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**CAMPUS JOURNALISM IN CAVITE PUBLIC HIGH SCHOOLS: A QUALITATIVE
CASE STUDY OF STAKEHOLDERS' PERSPECTIVES**

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28 July 2025

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Acceptance Page

This paper prepared by **CARLO JAY F. RUIZ** with the title: “**CAMPUS JOURNALISM IN CAVITE PUBLIC HIGH SCHOOLS: A QUALITATIVE CASE STUDY OF STAKEHOLDERS’ PERSPECTIVES**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Information and Communication Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree, Master of Development Communication.

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Biographical Sketch

Carlo Jay Frias Ruiz was born in Laoag City, Ilocos Norte, on June 12, 1992. He is the youngest of four children of Pepe R. Ruiz and Editha F. Ruiz. His sisters are Cherry Lou, Carolyn, and Chonalyn.

He spent his childhood in Laoag City, where he finished his primary and secondary education. After finishing high school, his parents transferred to Trece Martires City, Cavite. He earned a Bachelor of Arts in Mass Communication, major in Journalism, at Cavite State University-Main Campus. This strengthened his path as a writer and researcher.

In 2016, he completed a Certificate in Teaching Program, a post-baccalaureate program at Philippine Normal University-Manila. This qualified him to take and successfully pass the Board Licensure Examination for Professional Teachers (BLEPT). He was also accepted at the University of the Philippines Open University in 2021.

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In his free time, he enjoys writing blog articles, watching movies and musical plays, visiting food hubs and cafes, and conversing with friends.

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Dedication

This paper is dedicated to the people who brought me into this world and generously provided everything they could to nurture me—Tatay Pepe and Nanay Editha. You may not see the full value of your efforts, but I will forever cherish and appreciate you.

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Abstract

This qualitative case study explores the views of stakeholders which include student journalists, advisers, and school administrators, in secondary schools in Cavite, focusing on the implementation of campus journalism programs within the framework of the Campus Journalism Act of 1991.

The study aimed to examine the views and perspectives of the stakeholders, particularly in light of evolving technological advancements and the rise of digital media. Findings indicate a significant shift from print to online platforms, with students embracing digital publishing tools such as social media and AI-based applications.

Despite the benefits, stakeholders highlighted issues such as resource disparities, inadequate infrastructure, and insufficient professional training in digital media. Stakeholders expressed a shared belief in the need to amend the Campus Journalism Act of 1991 to better align with the digital age, emphasizing the importance of incorporating provisions for online publishing, digital censorship, and the ethical use of technologies like AI.

The study advocates for reforms in policy and the programs, proposing the integration of digital media into campus journalism training, enhanced resource allocation, and professional development for both students and educators. By addressing these gaps, the study sought to strengthen the role of campus journalism as a tool for student empowerment, media literacy, and civic engagement in the 21st century.

Keywords: Campus Journalism; Digital Media; Online Publishing; Campus Journalism Act.

Chapter I

INTRODUCTION

Background of the Study

Campus journalism has long played a significant role in shaping the lives of Filipino students, particularly at the secondary school level. It provides students with a platform to express their thoughts, develop critical thinking, and engage with social issues. Beyond just reporting news, campus journalism helps students develop a sense of responsibility and character, ultimately contributing to the formation of informed and responsible citizens. This aligns with the goals of Republic Act No. 7079, the Campus Journalism Act of 1991, which mandates schools to establish press organizations that give students a chance to practice journalism freely and responsibly. This Act also protects academic freedom, ensuring students can engage in journalistic activities without fear of censorship. The primary objectives of the law are to promote ethical journalism, protect free speech, and foster students' intellectual and personal growth.

However, while the Campus Journalism Act has served as the cornerstone of campus journalism in the Philippines, the media landscape has changed drastically since its enactment 34 years ago. The rise of digital media, social platforms, and online journalism has transformed how information is produced, consumed, and shared. Technological advancements have created a need for students to acquire a broader skill set that includes digital literacy, understanding of media ethics in online platforms, and mastery of digital publishing tools—all of which are essential for success in the modern media environment.

Several studies have highlighted the challenges that campus journalism programs face in adapting to this new era. Espadero (2022) and Cubillas and Cubillas (2021) explored issues such as lack of resources, overburdened teachers, and the gaps in teachers' knowledge about journalism, more particularly in underserved areas. These challenges are compounded by the absence of structured professional development for teachers and adequate tools and training for student journalists. Further, studies like Del Rosario (2021) emphasized how campus journalism helps develop critical thinking and creativity, but current programs still struggle with outdated resources and insufficient training in new media skills.

While the Campus Journalism Act of 1991 has laid the foundation for campus journalism, there is an increasing concern that the law no longer fully aligns with the needs of students today. As Espadero (2022) and Cubillas et al. (2018) suggested, the implementation of the law faces significant barriers, such as the lack of awareness about its provisions and insufficient institutional support. These studies suggest that the law's outdated framework fails to address the evolving role of journalism in the digital age. The incorporation of digital media into the curriculum and the Schools Press Conference (SPC) is one area that could greatly benefit from revisions to the Act, as Paguirigan and Paguirigan (2023) noted the importance of SPCs in raising awareness about campus journalism, but the existing support structures for such programs need to be strengthened.

Irrespective of such a body of work, a visibility gap in particular research is still present: very little is known about how stakeholders actually realize RA 7079 at the school level, supported by digital transformation in the background. Although the law stipulates the rights and duties, more has not been written the way student journalists, advisers, and school heads carry on and carry out the practice amidst schools.

Appreciation of these existed realities is imperative to an evaluation of the law as still relevant to empowerment of students and to educate democratic activeness amongst pupils in an environment of a fast-developing media.

Such a study also carves out clearly where it fits in the values of development communication. Campus journalism presents itself in participation, empowerment, and voice aspects in facilitating students to engage in the communication process directly, instilling critical literacy and advocacy skills in the students, and giving visibility to underrepresented points of view at the school level, respectively. Through stakeholder perspectives, the current research both conducted assessment of perspectives about RA 7079, as well as reflected on the role of campus journalism in supporting the construction of democratic and inclusive schools in accordance with the spirit of development communication.

Professional and academic background influences my interest toward campus journalism as a researcher. After experiencing, firsthand, the importance of student publications in fostering the critical thinking, creativity, and civic engagement level of learners, I was able to identify opportunities and limitations in the existing practice. My orientation as an educator and a communication researcher informs the paradigm with which I can relate to this study: the paradigm that recognizes the power differences among students, the advisers, and the administrators and urges the reforms to support the rights of student journalists in the time of digital era. This recoil attitude reinforces the question by positioning the study as an engaged and not as a detached observation process in order to ensure that there is a multifaction of the voice of stakeholders and as a contributor to significant educational and policy changes.

In light of these challenges and gaps, it is crucial to examine whether or not the Campus Journalism Act of 1991 needs updating to encompass digitalization, based

on the perspectives of those who comprise campus journalism in public high schools. As highlighted by Arao (2013) and Dasoy (2022), the existing law may need provisions for digital literacy, online ethics, and the inclusion of modern journalism tools in the curriculum. These updates would ensure that students gain the necessary skills to succeed in a rapidly changing media landscape.

This study aimed to explore the perspectives of stakeholders—student journalists, school paper advisers, and school administrators—in secondary schools in Cavite. Through this, the key provisions that could be incorporated into the law, such as integrating digital media training, improving online ethics education, and enhancing digital publishing capabilities in school programs, are highlighted.

By understanding the perspectives faced by campus journalism programs, the discussions will be further considered on how to modernize the law and ensure that students, as the primary stakeholders, are better equipped with the skills needed to thrive in the digital media age. This study further recommends updating the law and improving campus journalism programs, ultimately benefiting students and strengthening their role as responsible and critical members of society in the 21st century.

Statement of the Problem

In the Republic Act No. 7079 or Campus Journalism Act of 1991, campus journalism is understood as a crucial medium that guarantees freedom of expression and thought, as well as civic action among students. The available literature recognizes its role in enhancing literacy, innovation, and moral integrity in students. Nevertheless, most of the literature has either focused on the historical significance of the Act or the issue of resources and training. Although these studies pointed to

systemic barriers, there is also a scant literature on the actual perspectives and practice of the RA 7079 provisions in the school level amidst the current digital media landscape, especially by stakeholders such student journalists, advisers and school administrators.

This is a serious gap as the media have now transformed, and the situation is very different since 1991. The emergence of digital platforms, artificial intelligence, and the internet publication has altered the way journalism is being done, and yet, RA 7079 is more focused on print media. Unless knowingly how schools are facing these changes on the ground, no gauge can be placed on whether the law has kept alive students, preserved their rights, and brought about responsible journalism in the 21st century. Particularly, little is known on how student reporters manage to balance academic and journalistic obligations, on how advisers on how to fill the resources and training gaps, and on how administrators view their role of promoting campus journalism based on the premises of the Act.

This research is thus meaningful in the sense that it explores the views of the stakeholders within campus journalism in the province of Cavite, one of the most mobilized divisions in the country conducting press conferences and journalism contests. Through that, the study does not only cover a gap in the literature but also helps in the debate policies concerning restructuring RA 7079 in a way that may be more accommodating of realities these days. It not only identifies campus journalism as a subset of the larger value of development communication such as, participation, empowerment and voice, but also looks at whether contemporary practices are supporting these values in a digital age.

Therefore, the paper aimed to examine the perspectives of student journalists, school paper advisers, and school administrators concerning the application of RA

7079 in the technological change, and how those perspectives can be utilized to draw conclusions on how applicable, limiting, or futuristic the law is.

This research aimed to answer the question: How should campus journalism be improved in the digital era?

Specifically, this study addressed the following research questions:

1. How do the stakeholders engage with campus journalism programs in the context of evolving technological advancements?
2. How do the stakeholders view the relevance of the Campus Journalism Act of 1991 in today's digital age?
3. How do the stakeholders make sense of the ways digital media are being integrated into campus journalism programs?

Objectives of the Study

The objective of this study was to explore the perspectives and practices of stakeholders—student journalists, school paper advisers, and school administrators—in secondary schools in Cavite.

Specifically, the study aimed to:

1. investigate the practices of stakeholders in implementing campus journalism as stipulated in the Campus Journalism Act of 1991, amid technological advancements;
2. analyze the views of the stakeholders on the relevance of the Campus Journalism Act of 1991 in today's digital age, and explore what provisions should be incorporated into a revised version of the law; and

3. examine how digital media skills are integrated into the campus journalism program.

Significance of the Study

This study aimed to contribute to the growth of campus journalism by exploring the views and perspectives of the stakeholders, particularly in light of the evolving media landscape. A central argument of the research is that revising the Campus Journalism Act of 1991 could directly benefit students by equipping them with critical thinking, media ethics, and digital literacy skills that are crucial in today's media-driven society.

By addressing the challenges stakeholders face in the current educational context and exploring ways to update the law, the study contributes to discussions on reforming the Campus Journalism Act. The findings offer valuable insights and policy recommendations for improving campus journalism programs, ensuring that they remain relevant and responsive to the changing needs of students and the media industry. The results are expected to advocate for the integration of digital media training, media literacy, and ethical standards into the program, preparing students for the challenges of modern journalism.

The significance of the study is closely aligned with several of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), particularly:

SDG 4: Quality Education. This study is aligned with SDG 4, which aims to "ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all." Campus journalism programs promote critical thinking, creativity, and communication skills, which are essential components of quality education. By

advocating for reforms to the Campus Journalism Act, the research aims to ensure that campus journalism continues to be an effective educational tool, providing students with the necessary skills to thrive in a digital world. Additionally, it emphasizes the importance of equity in access to educational resources, especially in underserved areas, where the current provisions of the law may be insufficient.

SDG 16: Peace, Justice, and Strong Institutions. The study also contributes to SDG 16, which focuses on "promoting peaceful and inclusive societies for sustainable development, providing access to justice for all, and building effective, accountable, and inclusive institutions." By strengthening campus journalism programs, students can be empowered to participate in societal conversations, advocate for social justice, and foster democratic values. Revising the law would enhance the role of campus journalists in promoting transparency, accountability, and freedom of speech, helping to create informed, responsible citizens who are prepared to challenge systemic injustices and work towards sustainable development.

The findings of this study play a significant role in shaping the future of campus journalism, ensuring it remains not only a platform for student expression but also a powerful tool for personal, academic, and social development. By supporting the evolution of the Campus Journalism Act, the research aims to contribute to a more equitable, informed, and engaged student body, which can drive positive change in society.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

This paper had the following objectives. It was a monitoring exercise of the perspectives and practices of the stakeholders in their campus journalism programs according to the Republic Act 7079, also known as the Campus Journalism Act of

1991. The research aimed at finding out the issues in these institutions and offer advice on how the campus journalism program could be improved.

Schools were sampled among secondary schools with an existing campus journalism program in the Division of Cavite Province, Region IV-A (CALABARZON), especially those that were regarded as the best performing schools in campus journalism. The study was done between March and July 2025.

Chapter II

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

This chapter presents a review of literature related to the objectives of determining the perspectives and perceptions of campus journalists, school paper advisers, and school heads in campus journalism implementation at secondary schools in Cavite.

History of Campus Journalism

Journalism is considered an art of presenting news stories, documenting important events, gazing into the reality that takes place around the world, containing sensitive issues that may affect an enormous number of people, and serving the public interest. With a wide range of definitions, Journalism's purpose is considered to wield power, shape public opinion, and regulate the dissemination of informational or symbolic assets within society. It greatly serves democracy as it allows the public to be involved in the issues of the society (Cago, n.d.).

With the broad and important role of journalism comes its counterpart in schools—Campus Journalism. This entity serves as the training ground for students to be honed and molded as future journalism professionals. It is where they practice their young minds to analyze facts, interpret stories, express their opinion, and deliver well-crafted material for their own public.

Campus Journalism in the Philippines began with the University of Santo Tomas publishing *El Liliputiense* in 1890. However, Oscar Manalo, Narciso Matienzo, and Virgilio Monteloyola in *Ang Pamahayagan* (1985) contended that it started when the University of the Philippines published *The College Folio*, now known as *The*

Philippine Collegian, in 1910. They also mentioned that The Torch of the Philippine Normal University, The Guidon of the Ateneo de Manila University, and The Varsitarian of the University of Santo Tomas were published two years later. Regardless of which came first, Carlos Romulo y Pena edited The Coconut, the official student publication of Manila High School (now Araullo High School), which was published in 1912 and is considered the first and oldest high school newspaper in the country. In 1923, La Union High School in the Ilocos Region published The La Union Tab, marking the beginning of printed and regularly issued high school newspapers in the country. Since then, high school newspapers have continued to emerge (Esteban, n.d.).

Campus Journalism Act of 1991

Republic Act 7079, otherwise known as the Campus Journalism Act (CJA) of 1991 is the basis for the right of students to self-expression and their participation in news gathering and reporting. According to Balinas and Ibojo (2023), this paved way to the different school publications both in elementary and secondary schools. In Section 2 of the act, campus journalism's primary function is explicitly stated. This function aims to foster the growth and development of campus journalism as a tool to reinforce moral values, stimulate critical and imaginative thinking, and cultivate the moral character and self-discipline of Filipino youth.

Campus journalism faces challenges due to limited school funding, affecting student journalists and advisors' participation in events and creating awareness issues related to CJA. Furthermore, issues related to campus journalism funding are compounded by a lack of awareness concerning CJA, resulting in concerns such as the excessive workload of school paper advisors, the need for advisors to extend

beyond technical guidance in terms of content, and the insufficient institutional support from schools for campus journalism programs and activities. These issues are prevalent in both public and private elementary schools. The numerous difficulties and complexities surrounding campus journalism make it a significant area of study. Despite these challenges, there remains a scarcity of scholarly resources where comprehensive data on the state of campus journalism can be obtained (Espadero, n.d.).

Espadero (n.d.) further explained that public elementary school advisers perceive the issues and challenges in campus journalism as crucial for enhancing its implementation, especially in relation to teachers' learning and development. These professionals play a significant role in campus journalism within the educational setting.

In a study conducted by Cubillas et al. (2018) for several Elementary Schools in Butuan City, it has been found that the level of awareness concerning the provisions of Republic Act 7079 within educational institutions is directly related to their compliance. It has been observed that these factors can mutually influence each other.

Several factors impacting the implementation of campus journalism include structural challenges, such as delays in information dissemination and excessive teaching responsibilities; infrastructural difficulties, like insufficient journalism rooms for training and workshops, and a lack of necessary equipment (e.g., microphones, laptops, printers); and financial constraints, leading to poor publication circulation and low attendance of school paper advisers and student journalists.

Arao (2013), in his article *Reviewing the Campus Journalism Act of 1991*, sees the strengths and weaknesses of the said act. He pointed out the lack of funding to support the different campus press. Since the CJA uses the word “may”, schools may

refuse to collect funds from students. Thus, the inability to publish the articles that campus journalists are supposed to issue. He also revealed that in 2010, the College Editors Guild in the Philippines (CEGP) recorded 204 campuses press freedom violation cases nationwide, as reported by 42 respondent publications. Despite the lack of updated data on such violations, the information provided by the CEGP is disconcerting, especially considering the presence of a law designed to safeguard and uphold campus press freedom. Consequently, it is crucial to analyze various suggestions for either amending or repealing the CJA. Given that campus journalists still perspective harassment and intimidation, the CJA is perceived as ineffective for students and susceptible to misuse by educational institution officials.

In response, Kabataan Partylist Representative Raymond Palatino and Bayan Muna Representative Teodoro Casiño proposed House Bill No. 4287 on February 28, 2011. This bill suggests that while the Campus Journalism Act of 1991 contains strong provisions, it is "insufficient and lacking in essential aspects" to guarantee the continued existence of campus journalism. As stated in the bill's explanatory note, this legislation may be susceptible to manipulation by unscrupulous school administrators, potentially jeopardizing campus publications nationwide (Dasoy, 2022). The proposed legislation further aims to grant independence in managing finances, selecting published content, hiring staff, and appointing editorial board members for a student publication. Furthermore, it ensures that the publication's operations cannot be halted, suspended, or terminated due to the articles it publishes or the actions of its staff, unless proper procedures are followed.

Schools Press Conference

The school's press conference assumes a crucial role as a primary source of information, impacting the formation of opinions and guiding individual actions. The Campus Journalism act requires DepEd to sponsor and organize recurring competitions, press conferences, and training workshops. These events will involve writers and teacher-advisers of student publications from both elementary and secondary levels. Although affiliated with DepEd, it is distinct from the core education curriculum, emphasizing proficiency in writing and requiring active participation from student journalists, known as campus journalists.

In his keynote speech at the 2020 National Schools Press Conference held in Tuguegarao City, Education Undersecretary Diosdado San Antonio emphasized the importance of nurturing critical thinking skills in students through the development and strengthening of campus journalism programs. He underscored the pivotal role that student journalists play as instruments of empowerment for their communities, enabling them to produce news stories, feature articles, and various written and broadcast outputs (Molina, 2020).

In the same article, Molina (2020) added that by engaging in these activities, student journalists can ensure that their communities are well-informed and equipped to discern between authentic and misleading information, particularly amid the prevalence of fake news. San Antonio's remarks underscore the Department of Education's commitment to fostering a more critical and informed student population, ultimately contributing to the betterment of society as a whole.

In an article by Roguel (2022), the official student publication of Trece Martires City Senior High School (TMCSHS), *The Victors*, prepared for their participation at Division Schools Press Conference (DSPC) immediately as they return as a student

organization. The role of the organization is not limited to the school premises. The Campus Journalists (CJs) also look forward to joining the different categories of writing, cartooning, photojournalism, and broadcasting. Those who qualified on their local competitions or selected by their School Paper Adviser (SPA) will go through a series of training and coaching sessions weeks or even months before the DSPC. After the division level, depending on the set guidelines, winners will be representing their respective divisions to the Regional Schools Press Conference (RSPC). Subsequently, winners from the RSPC will be representing their respective regions to the National Schools Press Conference (NSPC). With this opportunity, CJs will not just acquire knowledge and develop their skills during the competition, they will have an opportunity to deal and build camaraderie with other CJs from different schools, both from public and private schools.

Campus Journalism Practices

Abad-Dadayan (2021), in the study *Campus Journalism Practices among State Universities of CALABARZON*, revealed the different activities conducted by Campus Journalists (CJs) in the tertiary level in terms of planning, management, production and distribution, participation in competitions, and budgeting.

In terms of planning, the study suggests that CJs must relate their by-laws to their “vision, values, and culture”. In its general assessment, their planning is moderately manifested. This was interpreted as fairly used or implies that campus journalists employ certain techniques as a method to accomplish a series of tasks. These tasks include fostering growth, reaching goals, addressing issues, and encouraging progress in their field of journalism within the campus environment. The

study suggests collaborative planning among the stakeholders with the practices of the CJs in the campus.

In the aspect of handling finances, the CJs are in need of assistance. Careful planning and financial management were identified to be areas to be improved (Abad-Dadayan, 2021).

In a study conducted by Untalan and Redulo (2019) entitled, *Performance of Secondary School Publications in Calapan City: Basis for Campus Journalism Development Plan*, the school papers of the Division of Calapan City in terms of disseminating information to students attained a “very high extent”. This has also been observed in disseminating information to parents and the community. This proves the relevance of the Campus Journalism program at the secondary level, not just in tertiary education. With the results of the study, the researchers suggest that schools should keep enhancing students' writing abilities, not just for academic journalism purposes, but also to guide them in their future careers. Furthermore, they also added that a comprehensive campus journalism development plan should be implemented in different schools.

The pivotal role of campus journalism programs and school publications encompasses the dissemination of pertinent information regarding campus events, the exposure of any misconduct, the upholding of accountability among leadership, and the communication of significant occurrences to the wider community. In order to fulfill these crucial functions, these publications must be granted autonomy and safeguarded from any editorial interference or censorship by administrative entities. (*The Foundation for Individual Rights and Expression*, n.d.). Hence, the need to further

explore the practices in the journalism program will greatly help identify the gaps among the concerned stakeholders.

In exploring the perspectives and perceptions of student journalists, advisers, and administrators or stakeholders in their practice and their compliance with the Campus Journalism Act of 1991; and in identifying the challenges and opportunities faced by campus journalism programs in adhering to the provisions of the Act, the quality of how they manage in serving their audience and their greater cause may be further improved.

Digital Transformation in Education and Media

It is now urgent that digital tools now be incorporated in the teaching of journalism in the 21st century. The adoption of artificial intelligence (AI), virtual reality (VR) and the appearance of augmented reality (AR) are technologies that are increasingly being included in educational programs across various curricula to orientate students towards the emerging media environment. Hossain, Wenger, and Senseman (2024) noted that AI, drone journalism, VR, and AR are expected to play a major role in the future of journalism curricula in 3 to 5 years. Nevertheless, various limitations still exist, such as long-term investments, prediction of shifts in technology, and faculty scarcity concerned with the necessary skills (Hossain, Wenger, and Senseman, 2024).

Journalism education throughout the world is keeping up with such changes in technology. An example is in Spain, where the universities are reconsidering their training models to include AI in video journalism training and education by highlighting

that new pedagogical models are required to apply talent fully in the training of these new technologies (Tejedor & Vila, 2021). However, in a study conducted in Turkey on the topic of AI introduction in journalism curricula, it was found that whereas some institutions had gone ahead in terms of integrating AI related courses, others differed in their implementation in terms of amount and manner (Kasneci et al., 2025).

The trends of digital journalism that are worldly are likewise apparent in the digital-first, social media, and citizen journalism. That is why improvement of the existing media laws is necessary to fit the digital era. The studies suggest that it is essential to modernize the laws related to the media, copyright and data protection in particular, due to the increase of the speed of digitalization of media content in a range of platforms and its establishment and development as the global distribution site (Wenger, Hossain, and Senseman, 2025).

Such new technologies as AI, VR, and AR do not only change the image of journalism but also redesign journalism education. Since these technologies are ever changing, it has become critical to ensure that learning institutions revise their curriculums to expose learners to the relevant skills to navigate and survive in the digital media environment.

Digital Literacy and Skills Development in Campus Journalism

Digital tools have come to dominate education in journalism, and this has been urgent in the 21st century. The rise of technologies in the classroom enables educators to integrate technologies like artificial intelligence (AI), virtual reality (VR), and augmented reality (AR) into their programs to ensure their students are ready to engage with the media world being complexified. According to a research conducted

by Hossain and Wenger and Senseman (2024), AI, drone journalists, VR, and AR are expected to make a considerable impact on journalism training in 3-5 years. But such pitfalls as the necessity of future investment, predicting technological changes, and the challenges of recruiting the required faculty with the necessary expertise remain (Hossain, Wenger, and Senseman, 2024).

Education of journalism in the world is taking advantage of these technological innovations. Another example is found in Spain, where universities are re-evaluating how they approach training to bring AI into the video journalism training with an imperative on new pedagogical methods in which such augmented technologies can be effectively taught (Tejedor & Vila, 2021). Likewise, a research paper in Turkey examined acceptance of AI in journalism education and identified that whereas individual universities have gone beyond and federalized discussions of AI-related courses, the degree and manner in which they are doing so differs across universities (Kasneci et al., 2025).

The worldwide digital trends in the journalism sphere could be seen also in the turn towards digital-first reporting, the role of social media in distributing news and in the emergence of citizen journalism. These advancements require new changes in the application of current media laws to fit in the digital era. Studies reveal a need to update laws that are relevant to media adaptation, such as copyright and data protection laws as crucial metrics to confront the rapid digitalization of media contents and emergence of online distribution globally through different technological platforms (Wenger, Hossain, and Senseman, 2025).

Emerging technologies like AI, VR, and AR are not only transforming journalism practices but also reshaping journalism education. As these technologies continue to

evolve, it is essential for educational institutions to adapt their curricula to equip students with the necessary skills to navigate and thrive in the digital media landscape.

Ethical Issues in Digital Journalism for Students

The emergence of digital tools in journalism education has raised some thorny ethical questions. Among these are the chances that the students unintentionally or intentionally create inaccurate material. The accessibility of information and its transferability on the internet may result in the spreading of fake news particularly when students use sources that cannot be verified or turn to unexpected judgment regarding the information they come across (Gutierrez-Caneda, 2024). Additionally, the adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) applications, e.g. ChatGPT, in journalism has put the questions of authorship and plagiarism on the agenda. The content created by AI can already resemble human writing, which is why it becomes hard to tell whether a piece of writing was successfully completed by students, or it was produced by machines. This violence is making the academic integrity policies much harder to enforce, as well as upholding the historic ideas about authorship (Zhou, 2024).

In addition, the application of AI to journalism training requires the reconsideration of the ethical principles. The use of AI can improve the efficiency and creativity of the work, but there is also the risk of bias, privacy invasion, and possible consequences of its abuse. The task of educators is to work on new frameworks that would support the responsible use of AI and protect journalistic norms (Stahl, 2024).

Bullying of student journalists online continues to be a ubiquitous problem. Online anonymity can encourage people to commit online bullying and other online abuse types, as well. It has been shown that student journalists are especially

susceptible to such attacks with their attack potentially harming their mental health and well-being (Hill, 2025). As a reaction, schools are putting in place policies and programs that would prevent the harassment of online students. As an example, the United Independent School District in Texas introduced a new task force named DigiWise that aims to improve the safety of students on-line and teach them how to be responsible when using technologies. The plan is to fight cyberbullying, encourage proper screen time behavior by spreading goodness online (Laredo Morning Times, 2025).

Moreover, legal frameworks are evolving to address the challenges posed by online harassment. Some jurisdictions have enacted laws specifically targeting cyberbullying, providing clearer guidelines for schools and institutions to follow when addressing such incidents (Super Lawyers, 2025). These legislative measures underscore the importance of creating a safe and supportive environment for student journalists to practice their craft without fear of online retaliation.

Impact of Digital Journalism on Student Engagement and Learning

Digital media at campus journalism has greatly changed the interaction, creativity, and cooperation among students. Blogs, podcasts, and YouTube have become a new favor among student journalism with opportunities to be creative and engage the audience. Students' studies who suggest an indispensable role of intrinsic motivation debate show that social media use increases student creativity and their academic engagement (Gulzar, 2022). Also, social media can be used as an aid to collaborative learning in students, allowing to establish interaction between them and form joint knowledge (Ahmed Khan, 2025).

But the trade-off between studies and extracurricular activities such as campus journalism is still a controversial matter. Research has indicated that academic performance is potentially affected positively by participating in extracurricular activities, but the level of such effects can be both positive and negative (Nassar, 2025). Campus journalism becomes an issue when students' perspective makes it difficult to balance journalistic work and studying. The balancing act highlights the importance of institutional level support in the effort to make sure that students are able to enjoy both academic and extra-curricular perspectives without putting their well-being or academic achievement at a hazard.

Institutional Support and Training for Digital Journalism

The use of digital tools in journalism education is now urgent in the 21st century. Nevertheless, these technological changes are making most teachers find it hard to cope. A survey conducted by Siregar and Siregar (2024) also found that individual teaching perspectives among teachers resulted in a huge gap in the levels of digital literacies. Most educators often lack the essential digital skills needed for effective technology integration, and many professional development programs tend to emphasize theoretical knowledge over practical application. Weak infrastructure and weak institutional backing are other factors that add to the challenge to integrate digital media efficiently. The results of the study suggested that eliminating them has to be achieved through a set of multifaceted measures, such as professional growth aimed towards empowering educators, the investment of infrastructures, and creating institutional encouragement (Siregar and Siregar, 2024).

On the same note, a research study conducted by Muyambi and Ramorola (2025) assessed the willingness of educators who are based in South Africa to embrace the teaching of digital media. The results produced great differences as to accessibility to digital resources and availability of technical skills and awareness of e-learning policies by the educators. The various differences make it difficult to equitably integrate digital media in teaching and secondary training and implementation of policies to close these gaps is a requirement (Muyambi & Ramorola, 2025).

Sharing of resources is also of vital concern in digital reservation of journalism education. Amidst the growing enrollment, constrained budgets, and sustainability objectives, in many learning institutions, searching methods have to do with administrative decision-making and resource management that must be much more efficient than before. To solve these issues, Koukaras et al. (2025) presented a conceptual view on smart management of the campus that combines Artificial Intelligence (AI) and enhanced wireless networks using 5G. This framework will help to transform the sphere of educational management by increasing the level of asset distribution and minimizing the decision-making process (Koukaras et al., 2025).

Moreover, the COVID-19 pandemic has exacerbated resource allocation issues in higher education. The decline in enrollments has affected schools' ability to achieve their academic missions, leading to a crisis in many institutions. QuadC (2023) discussed how big data reporting can help reveal students' learning styles, enhance enrollment within specific departments, and increase retention rates, thereby transforming resource allocation in higher education (QuadC, 2023).

Campus Journalism as a Tool for Civic Engagement

Campus journalism can significantly encourage the ideals of democracy and social responsibility among the junior and senior high school students in the Philippines. Learners actively pursue topical issues in the society through student publications, which turns them into critical thinkers, expose them to the ethical responsibilities of reporting, and give them hands-on exercise of resisting what society considers illegal. As an example, the National Schools Press Conference (NSPC) as an organization created by Republic Act No. 7079, is where students in different parts of the country come together to express their skills in journalism and to raise their questions about issues as not only social justice but also the environment. This yearly event ignites the significance of student journalism in supporting the ideologies of democracy as well as persuading young people to participate in the affairs of the society (Seráfica, 2006).

In addition, journalism in campus can be an effective communication channel of media literacy to the students. Student reporters are able to train and devise effective analytical abilities by writing content that critically reflects on the happenings and things happening in society. Programs such as Healthy NewsWorks are built on the understanding of media literacy that helps the students learn how to make news and should consider the consequences of their actions in terms of ethic. Through such efforts, students are likely able to become critical consumers and producers of media that puts into their arsenal the means to read, creatively and critically, through condensation and interpretation filter the vast and vexed media (Molina, 2020; Seráfica, 2006).

Relevance of the Campus Journalism Act of 1991 in the Digital Age

The Campus Journalism Act of 1991 (Republic Act No. 7079) was signed to defend the press freedom at campus level and foster the growth and continued expansion of campus journalism in the Philippines. Nevertheless, the swift evolution of digital media has unveiled huge loopholes in the law especially with regards to online media and social media. The founding act mainly talks about the print media, exposing student journalists in the digital world to censorship and suppression (Dagli, 2024).

An evaluation of the adoption of RA 7079 in high schools demonstrated that on the one hand, the law requires the creation of student publications, but on the other hand, there are no detailed instructions concerning online services. This has left loopholes in protection of the rights of student journalists over the internet (Valeza, 2021). Furthermore, lack of clear comments on the digital media has led to cases whereby the school officials have been overly persuasive to online publications, compromising freedoms of the numbers (Rico, 2024).

To address this issue, an amendment called Campus Press Freedom Act was put forward to supplant the RA 7079. This seeks to be a piece of legislation that will secure editorial independence, Bungard digital publishing, safeguard sustainable funding and hold the perpetrators liable. It aims to transform the inadequacy of the law enacted in 1991 as it seeks stronger law standards that suit the contemporary world of digitality (Center for Media Freedom and Responsibility, 2025).

To protect the freedom of student journalists in a digital age, legal experts and media advocates have pointed to the need to revise the Campus Journalism Act to keep it current. The student publications are vulnerable to censorship and supremacy

without legislative reforms to advance the idea of promoting democracy and critical thinking in young people (Dagli, 2024).

Comparative Analysis of Print versus Digital Campus Journalism

The digitization of campus journalism and the elimination of print applications in higher education have been a major change in the educational arena especially in the Philippines. This change has been influenced by the progressive rise of new avenues in the digital arena and the need of student magazines to fit into the current trends of media consumption.

Colleges and universities have begun adopting a digital format of campus journalism, using platforms such as blogs, social media, and independent college and university-focused websites to distribute information. Canete and Dizon (2024) conducted a study of digital publishing tool integration in Philippine universities, which delineates the opportunities and challenges of this change. The study established that the digital platforms have a wider coverage and real-time possibilities in publication; they are also associated with difficulties concerning digital literacy among the students and establishing the constant training of multimedia journalism skills.

In addition, the COVID-19 pandemic brought forth greater digitalization of campus journalism. A good quantity of student publications switched to online formats in order to continue their activities during the lockdown. This not just provided a lifeline to the campus journalism but has also highlighted the significance of digital literacy in recent education.

Student involvement and participation in campus journalism have been significantly affected by the shift towards digital platforms. Digital platforms enable

real-time engagement and response with feedback and makes the perspective somewhat interactive and participatory on the part of student reporters. In another study, Reyes and Santos (2023) investigated how digital platforms impacted students' engagement in campus journalism and concluded that student engagement and interest showed to be more visible and active when digital tools were being used to produce and share content. The study highlighted how online platforms do not only increase the network of the student publication but also empower students in ways to engage their readers.

However, the transition to digital journalism also presents challenges. The same study by Reyes and Santos (2023) noted that while digital platforms offer numerous benefits, they also require students to develop new skills and adapt to rapidly changing technologies. This necessitates ongoing support and training to ensure that students can fully leverage digital tools in their journalistic endeavors.

The shift from print to digital formats in campus journalism represents a significant evolution in how student publications operate and engage with their audiences. While this transition offers numerous advantages, including broader reach and enhanced student participation, it also presents challenges that require careful consideration and support. Educational institutions must continue to invest in digital literacy programs and provide the necessary resources to ensure that student journalists can navigate the digital landscape effectively.

Role of the DepEd's Schools Press Conference in the Digital Age

The Schools Press Conference (SPC) of the Department of Education has shaped much in the digital era without availing changes to the available technology and improved the perspective of online journalism in the campus department. The

SPC was conventionally organized as a face-to-face event, but the COVID-19 pandemic forced the SPC to shift to the virtual form. In August 2021, the National Schools Press Conference (NSPC) was the first of its current kind, with members using the internet offering webinars, contests, and debates on the topic of responsible journalism and ethical use of social media. This transformation not only provided continuity of journalistic training reserve in difficult periods but also brought a more accessible and inclusive nature of campus journalism making it available to a greater number of regions.

The adoption of digital media in SPC competitions has added some significantly different fields of student activity and content production. Incorporation of multimedia types, including online publishing and television broadcasting, indicates the recent need to emphasize more on the role of digital literacy in teaching journalism. These groups can prompt students to acquire their skills in digital storytelling, multimedia production, and online content management, which comply with all the tendencies of education in journalism nowadays that focuses on supporting digital skills (Tang, 2023). Furthermore, the greater popularity of social media in marketing the work of students has contributed to the greater outreach and influence of SPC participants, who now could disseminate their journalistic creations among more people and establish the culture of being a digital citizen among young people.

Sustainability of Campus Journalism Programs

The sustainability of the campus journalism programs in the Philippines has been noted to be a major challenge thereby touching on the areas of funding and sharing of resources. A lot of schools still face the challenge of poor financial provision

even after the passing of the Campus Journalism Act of 1991, which requires that student publishing be instituted. Callo and Carlobos (2025) point out that the problem of funding, equipment shortage, and inadequate training possibilities for school publications in Laguna state elementary schools are obstacles to effective and sustainable school publications. The situations of such restrictions tend to lead to poor quality and decreased involvement in the journalism processes.

In reaction to such predicaments, there are educational institutions which have explored other sources of funds and collaborations. As an example, the Government of Canada with the Xavier University - Ateneo de Cagayan established environmental journalism training systems in the climate-prone regions and offered means and resources to aspiring campus journalists. These programs are an acknowledgement of the possibilities of combining efforts between government institutions and businesses to make college journalism more sustainable.

Altogether, the adoption of digital media into the journalism of the campuses has been a prerequisite when it comes to long-term sustainability. Advincula and Adtoon (2024) highlighted crises suggesting the role and significance of digital readiness and flexibility among publication advisers in universities and colleges in which surgeons who adopted technological systems and tools managed to keep students engaged in campus communication and publication quality compared to those that did not adopt technology. Such a move towards online platforms is not only increasing the coverage area of student publications, but also in line with the changing media that is showing relevant media continuity that suits the relevance of campus journalism programs.

Gaps in Existing Literature

Despite the fact that Campus Journalism Act of 1991 (RA 7079) is best accepted to be the foundation of student journalism in the Philippines, most of the existing body of study focused more towards describing the provisions and historical significance of the bill compared to the context of its present use. Arao (2013) and Dasoy (2022) also focus on the active position of the law in legally recognized student press freedom and institutionalization of school publications without discussing the operationalization of the Act at the school level. This is more so because the law was promulgated at a pre-digital age, and it is silent on certain matters like the issue of online journalism, multimedia publishing and the digital ethics.

The second disparity is in the consideration of the role of the stakeholders. Much attention is given to the personal individual work of students, advisers, and administrators, and Del Rosario (2021) asserts the importance of developing the critical thinking and creativity of students, Espadero (2022) focuses on the part of advisors in drafting publications, and Cubillas and Cubillas (2021) outline the role played in resource distribution by administrators. Nevertheless, such works tend to look at the stakeholders individually and not look at interactive interactions. Still not investigated is the effect of these relationships to decision-making, publication sustenance and general campus journalism practices.

Repeated difficulties like insufficient funds, insufficient quality advice training, and teacher workload are also mentioned in the literature (Espadero, 2022; Cubillas and Cubillas, 2021). The same situation with international studies where resources and institutional constraints are mentioned in situations like Kenya (Ochilo, 2019) and South Africa (Teer-Tomaselli, 2018). However, these studies mostly end at

identification of problems, and the ways in which schools face these were seldom explored, what are the coping mechanisms utilized by various stakeholders, and how the institutional context challenges them or worsens their conditions.

The other huge discrepancy is the one in relation to digital and media literacy. Although Philippine research up to now (e. g. Del Rosario, 2021; Dasoy, 2022) recognizes the increasing intake of digital publishing and online ethics, empirical studies of how schools implement these competencies practically into campus journalism under the RA 7079 are consistent. How the multimedia practices have been incorporated in the practices of student publications in the United States (Schmidt, 2020) and the United Kingdom (Buckingham, 2019) are shown, there are still very few studies involving this population in the Philippines. Such a lack is of relevance to whether Filipino student journalists are becoming presentable enough to work in modern media environments.

Lastly, although the views of students and freedom of press are worldwide issues (Lidsky, 2016; Teer-Tomaselli, 2018), not many studies undertaken in comparison to Benigno (Philippines) allow linking these two to the situation there. The literature fails to analyze how Filipino student journalists can negotiate their press freedom, empowerment, and participation within their own unique cultural and institutional setting adequately, making the bigger picture of how campus journalism in the Philippines can conform or deviate from international practices.

Overall, even though the literature confirms the importance of campus journalism as a both educational and democratic practice, several gaps are still observed in discourse on how RA 7079 is practiced, the role tied with stakeholder relationship in shaping school-based journalism, how individual institutions are adapting to existing challenges, digital and media literacy assimilation in campus

journalism programs, and overlap of practices in the Philippines with world trends. The proposed study fills these gaps by exploring the issue of campus journalism at Cavite secondary schools using the prism of development communication, focus on participation, empowerment, and voice.

Synthesis

The analyzed literature confirms the fact that campus journalism is crucial in advancing the freedom of expression and critical thinking as well as civic engagement among the students. Including the Campus Journalism Act of 1991, which is also known as Republic Act 7079, the policy framework of the student publications is legitimizing student press organizations and securing the right and freedom of participation in journalistic endeavors (Arao, 2013; Dasoy, 2022). The educational importance of campus journalism has been attested to by scholars, who convene to support their argument with accurate claims about the role of campus journalism in the growth of literacy levels, creativity, leadership, and democracy (Del Rosario, 2021; Espadero, 2022).

Meanwhile, the literature helps to focus on the place played by stakeholders in the formation of campus journalism. The skill development and self-expression opportunities benefit the students, advisers and facilitators serve roles as their mentors and facilitators, and administrators have the roles of provision of the institutional support and resources (Cubillas and Cubillas, 2021). However, such roles are usually studied separately not as interdependent, and the interactions they have on sustainability and quality of school publications are ignored.

Such areas as difficulties with practice also have sufficient descriptions, with resource lack, lack of adviser training, and instructor workload being often mentioned as obstacles (Espadero, 2022; Cubillas & Cubillas, 2021). These concerns can be reflected in international research, indicating that there are financial and institutional constraints in Kenya (Ochilo, 2019) as well as South Africa (Teer-Tomaselli, 2018). Nevertheless, these studies outline repeat issues but seldom discuss how schools can accommodate their recurrent problems or the strategies given by the stakeholders to continual their journalism programs.

Another area of concern is integrating digital and media literacy. Experts agree that the role of online publishing and online ethics has become substantially more important in campus journalism (Del Rosario, 2021; Dasoy, 2022). Global research presents the examples relating to the development of student journalism towards the use of multimedia and digital platforms in such countries as the United States (Schmidt, 2020) and the United Kingdom (Buckingham, 2019). However, Philippine studies are still scanty in depicting concrete ways schools implement digital practices within campus journalism in accordance with RA 7079.

Lastly, the globalist view reemphasizes the significance of student voice and press liberty as two principles that are global in nature (Lidsky, 2016; Teer-Tomaselli, 2018). Although these are what enable student publications to be seen as democratic, little research has attempted to compare these perspectives abroad with those in the Philippines. The latter leads to very limited knowledge of how the Filipino student journalists struggle to balance press freedom, empowerment, and involvement in their specific institutional and cultural context.

Collectively, the literature gives a very powerful base to perceive the significance of campus journalism and fails to fill the gaps that exist. The

operationalization of RA 7079 on the school-level, the relationship between the stakeholders and the journalism practices, institutional adjustment to insurmountable challenges, and implementation of digital and media literacy in the programs and the comparative global trends are not thoroughly analyzed. This paper aims to fill these uncertainties by analyzing how and in what environments the implementation of campus journalism in Cavite studying schools pursued, taking its perspectives in the development communication ideologies: participation, empowerment, and voice.

Chapter III

METHODOLOGY

This chapter presents the procedures that the researcher followed to attain the objectives of this study on the stakeholders' perspectives in campus journalism implementation.

Research Design

This research employed the qualitative case study method, which is suitable when analyzing complex phenomena related to social life in the real world. Case study design permits a descriptive inquiry into the processes, practices, and situations of campus journalism programs in chosen secondary schools in the province of Cavite. Rather than abstract perspectives, the study examined the perspectives of various stakeholders on the relevance of Campus Journalism Act of 1991 in today's digital age, practice of campus journalism amid technological advancements, and their sensemaking of the integration of digital media into their campus journalism programs.

The case study approach was chosen to perform a closer approach to the issue of implementing campus journalism in the context of Campus Journalism Act of 1991, particularly concerning the problems and opportunities the digital media present. This design offers the ease of dealing with a variety of viewpoints—that of student journalists, advisers, and school heads—while placing their actions within larger institutional and policy contexts.

The semi-structured interviews with the participants, direct observations of their practice and publication, and reviews of documents such as articles published and

other materials were used to collect data. This multidimensional approach helped examine a wide range of areas in campus journalism such as organizational affairs, use of resources, the practice of publications, and the incorporation of digital media. The process of data collection focused on insights into the way that these practices are implemented, facilitated, or limited in the schools.

Overall, the research design emphasizes a study of campus journalism as a process rooted in learning institutions and influenced by policy technological factors and organizational backgrounds. This case study intended to offer a grounded knowledge of the implementation process and maintenance of campus journalism in Cavite secondary schools.

Participants of the Study

The researcher involved three groups of people from the public high schools in Cavite Province, specifically campus journalists, school paper advisers, and school administrators. Some preset selection criteria were used to ensure that the participants were engaged in campus journalism extensively and could offer insights that are pertinent to the practices and situations of the mentioned sphere.

Campus Journalists (five participants): All secondary students who had successfully completed at least three years of campus journalism program in high school and attended the Division or higher-level Schools Press Conference. The long-term engagement they had made them conversant with the workings of student publications, in print and online.

School Paper Advisers (five participants): Teachers who had been given the role at least three years actively in a row as the advisers of school publications. There were these participants who had the duty of guiding the students on how to write, edit, and manage publications, and assisting them in their participation in press conferences and other journalism-related activities.

School Administrators (five participants): School administrators who were upfront supervisors of the campus journalism programs within their schools. They were invited because they grant resources and help comply with the RA 7079, and thus, ensuring the institutional support of the activities of the campus journalism.

The number of participants, in total, was 15: five teachers; five students; and five student journalists, five school paper advisers, and five school administrators. This agreed representation would make possible the stakeholder groups to have equal representation, and thus, would enable the study to investigate the interactions, practices, and contexts of shaping campus journalism in Cavite secondary schools.

Locale of the Study

The study was done in the selected secondary schools in the Division of Cavite Province, Region IV-A (CALABARZON). The study site was selected to be Cavite due to its positive involvement in the journalism-related activities such as Schools Press Conference in the division, regional, and national levels. The division has always been quite ardent in the area of student journalism, and it is a suitable place to explore how Campus Journalism Act of 1991 is being practiced.

The criteria used to identify the schools represented in the current research were the existence of developed campus journalism programs with active student

publications and involvement in journalism-related activities. The selection of schools did not primarily aim to showcase only those that have successful campus journalism programs, but rather to offer reflective and significant settings for examining the processes, school-based challenges, and prospects of launching journalism in campus under the RA 7079 in a digital age.

Research Instrument

A semi-structured interview guide was designed and applied to every respondent to collect data for this study. The guide was intended on how campus journalism is being implemented in relation to the practices, processes, and contexts based on Campus Journalism Act of 1991. It included questions grouped into three categories, namely, (1) the difficulties and prospects faced in putting the campus journalism programs into practice, (2) opinions of what School Press Conference can do to create awareness and facilitate implementation of RA 7079, and (3) proposals to bolster campus journalism in the digital era.

Annex F of this research contains the interview guide. Research experts had to confirm its usefulness before its utilization to give it clarity, relevance, and appropriateness. Demographic data including the role, years of working in the company and gender was also gathered to put the perspectives of participants in perspective.

Data Gathering Procedures

This study involved semi-structured interviews related to the data collection to gather the necessary information on research participants (n= 15): five student journalists, five school paper advisers and five school administrators. The length of the

interviews was also between 30 minutes and an hour which was also enough time to discuss vital points without going off track with regard to the aims of the research. Research interviews were carried out through interviews based on the accessibility and choice of the respondents.

All interviews were recorded with the consent of the participants on tape so that there was no inaccuracy in recording responses. The recordings were transcribed verbatim to analyze it later. All the participants were informed of the purpose of the study, which was voluntary. Before conducting the interviews, formal approval was obtained in collaboration with the Department of Education Division of Cavite, and letters of consent were provided to all participants. They were all anonymized in the results of this study. The names used in the statements are all pseudo names.

Semi-structured interviews allowed flexibility in exploring more on particular issues and at the same time ensuring that no significant issues were omitted. Using the method facilitated gathering of in-depth knowledge concerning the structure, maintenance, and application of campus journalism to the setting in which high school students' study in Cavite.

Data Analysis

Reflexive thematic analysis was utilized in analyzing data which is in line with the description suggested by Braun and Clarke (2006). The analytic procedure prioritized the development of themes within the dataset systematically and transparently and concentrated on the practices, processes and contexts of journalism implementation at colleges and universities instead of concentrating on the unsubstantiated assertions about inner states.

The steps of analysis were made in six consecutive phases:

Familiarization. The transcription of the audio recording was made word-to-word, and the researcher read all the transcriptions and field notes many times to have the broad picture of the data. At this phase, analytic memos were prepared to document first impressions and the possible directions on the analysis.

Generating initial codes. The transcripts were commercially coded in an inductive method throughout the whole data. The codes reflected on valuable elements of organizational routine, resource management, practices around publication, utilization of digital tools, policy interpretation, and communication with the stakeholders. This was created as a working codebook, which included code names and definitions along with illustrative extracts, and was updated during analysis.

Searching for themes. Codes that were related would be collected and used to create candidate themes which captured patterns of responses when participants were asked to respond (e.g., "resource allocation and funding practices," "digital skills and training and the various ways in which participants can respond to a group of questions). Thematic map was created in order to visualize the relations between candidate themes and subthemes.

Reviewing themes. Review of candidate themes was completed in two steps, namely (a) verification of the coherence of coded extracts within a single theme and (b) validation of individual themes in the entire data set. In the process of review, qualifying themes were merged, refined and others rejected as they had no adequate supporting data.

Defining and naming themes. End themes had a clear definition containing a description of the scope and bounds of the end themes. A name was issued to each theme and a note which explained how the theme discussed the research focus.

Producing the report. Thematically relevant writing ups were performed that mutually classified findings and discussions on policy-related literature. The samples of the representatives of groups were chosen to represent each theme and show the analytic interpretation.

Procedures to ensure rigor. The study used various methods to enhance the credibility of the results: methodological triangulation (interviews, observations, review of documents); the preservation of an audit trail future versions of transcripts, a codebook, analytic memos); peer debriefing with the thesis adviser and other participants; and documentation of coding decisions. In as many instances as possible, the participants were provided with the option of reviewing their interview transcript and providing their comments on initial summaries.

Positionality and researcher reflexivity. Reflexive practice was used to recognize the positionality held by the researcher as well as to control possible effects of the positionality on the interpretation of the data. The researcher, who is a teacher and a communication researcher, and has a professional interest in campus journalism, maintains a reflexive journal which he uses to document his assumptions, decisions, and biases that emerged during analysis. It countered potential forms of bias (e.g., a likelihood to approach the idea of digital integration in a positive way or prioritize the framings of empowerment) by (a) searchingly pursuing disconfirming data in the dataset, (b) discussing interpretations with the thesis adviser and colleagues and (c) recording other readings in analytic memos. The reflexive actions enhance concern over the process in which the conclusions had been derived, and they will

narrow down the scope between the descriptive findings and the interpretive remarks the researcher presents themselves.

The combination of the two procedures generated a formal, clear thematic analysis adept at analyzing the practice and contexts of campus journalism application within the digital age through the RA 7079.

Chapter IV

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter presents the perspectives and practices of student journalists, school paper advisers, and school administrators in Cavite secondary schools that have campus journalism programs. Based on the data analysis, vital themes were identified, highlighting the outlook of the participants, issues they are facing, and their ambitions. The context of such findings is the Campus Journalism Act of 1991 and the effects of new changes induced by digital media.

Stakeholders' Practice of Campus Journalism Amid Technological Advancements

This part of the paper reveals key themes about the practices and experiences of stakeholders in implementing their campus journalism programs amid the ever-changing technology. It also considers their perspectives on how the Campus Journalism Act of 1991 can be modified despite the increasing modern-day media demands and, in the years to come.

Digital-First by Necessity, Not by Design

The transition to digital-first publishing in campus journalism had nothing to do with a strategic plan. Instead, they employed this practice to make do with their limited resources and to adapt to technological trends. The shift from print to online publishing was a response to the need for greater reach, quicker dissemination, and adaptability to increasingly accessible digital tools. Students, advisers, and school administrators

all acknowledged that although digital publishing presented possibilities for greater visibility, it also created new challenges such as managing feedback in real time and verifying available materials on the internet. The scarcity of resources, especially when it comes to materials used to print books and money, meant that many schools resorted to free online platforms, such as social media, to help them with disseminating news and information. This shift to digital- first publishing became a necessity in line with the broader trend in the educational and media environments where digital platforms are becoming invaluable and crucial in their day-to-day operations.

- “We publish online now—no more printed issues—because it’s faster and more people see it.” (Jenna, Student, School 2)
- “Our page gets comments in minutes. It’s great, but students end up moderating and verifying in real time.” (Marco, Adviser, School 1)
- “We still print one year-end issue for parents; everything else is digital.” (Ben, School Administrator, School 5)
- “We had to switch to digital because we couldn’t afford to print anymore. Social media was the easiest and cheapest option.” (Abby, Student, School 2)
- “The print edition became too costly, so we started using Facebook for school announcements and news.” (Sir Coco, School Administrator, School 3)

The information shows that the decision to go digital was a pragmatic change and not a strategy for the future. While digital platforms like social media offered the benefits of speed and reach, it also created new complexities, especially in terms of content moderation and the fact-checking process. Students and advisers shared experiences of increased workloads, with students taking on the responsibility of

moderating real-time comments and verifying information, which are extensions of the duties of campus journalists at a time of digitalization and information superhighway. This shift was not always a smooth one, with some schools still printing out a limited number of issues for specific purposes such as year-end editions, but the general trend was towards digital-first due to resource constraints. The juxtaposition of the contrasting cases brings to light how, although there are still schools that use print for certain things, such as events, the trend of digital media publications in schools is undeniable and recognized as a strong and necessary future for campus journalism.

In the context of the digital age, this shift highlights a larger challenge facing modern education, which is what to do with the balance of technological advancements and what resources are needed to effectively implement them. Schools having better access to technology and infrastructure were able to adapt faster as others struggled due to limited resources, which points to the growing digital divide between institutions. For a lot of schools, and for schools that have fewer financial resources, it had less to do with innovation and more to do with survival; they leveraged free online platforms such as Facebook and Google Sites to reach their audience. This forced adaptation, however, also allowed for greater community engagement, as students were able to reach a greater audience outside the physical boundaries of their schools and extend their impact and engagement in the public discourse.

This shift is in line with trends in journalism education more generally, where the use of digital platforms is being increasingly understood as a key for reaching audiences but that also brings new challenges in content verification and ethical journalism (Schmidt, 2020). Studies have found that although digital tools can allow

greater opportunities for engagement, they also come with additional responsibilities on students to manage their online interactions and raise questions about the amount of training that there must be for responsible digital publishing (Buckingham, 2019).

The transition to a digital-first approach to publishing in campus journalism brings to the fore the necessity for RA 7079 to adapt and include provisions for digital media, online ethics, and content moderation training. Policymakers and educators should include digital journalism in the curriculum so that students know not only how to use digital platforms, but also to understand the ethical responsibilities and considerations associated with using these.

Advisers as Mentors and Mediators

Advisers in campus journalism programs are pivotal players and mentors as well as gatekeepers in balancing students' editorial freedom with institutional expectations and policies. They are responsible not only for guiding students in writing, editing, and creating content online, but also for making sure that the policies of the school's administration are adhered to, especially in sensitive or controversial areas. Advisers are fundamental to the survival of campus journalism programs, especially in schools with less resources, where they also are needed to step in and handle logistical issues like gaining funding and equipment. While advising students to be autonomous, they also act as mediators between the students and the school administration, ensuring that student publications do not perform beyond rules and regulations. This balancing act is critical because while advisers want to support students, encouraging the growth of their journalism, they must also keep the

institution's rules in mind while helping those same students preserve the overall quality of the publication.

- “We’re not just writing and meeting deadlines; we’re also making sure students don’t overstep boundaries set by the administration.” (Marco, Adviser, School 1)
- “Advisers wear many hats. We guide them in writing, editing, and making sure they don’t get into trouble with the administration.” (Ma’am Junnie, Adviser, School 3)
- “Sometimes, we’re more like administrators than journalists. We need to make sure we have funding, manage the technical side, and keep the content appropriate.” (Sir Ronnie, Adviser, School 4)
- “I try to encourage students to express their views freely, but I also have to consider what the administration would allow.” (Ma’am Erika, Adviser, School 2)
- “It’s a lot of work, balancing the editorial side with what the school wants from us. But we have to keep things in check.” (Marco, Adviser, School 1)

The data shows the importance of advisers in preserving the balance between the autonomy of students and the control of the institution. Their role extends beyond content production. They are responsible for making sure that the journalistic freedom of the students does not conflict with the policies and values held by the school administration. While advisers strongly support student empowerment, they are also obligated to navigate the numerous delicate dynamics between editorial independence and institutional oversight. This has become particularly clear in

schools that struggle with less resources and thus rely on their advisers to make up the gap in funding, equipment, and training. The duties of advisers are therefore multifaceted, consisting of both technical knowledge in journalism, as well as the capacity to maintain good institutional relationships to keep a functioning, sustainable publication.

The presence of the adviser as a gatekeeper is key in student journalism whether to moderate content produced or not. Their dual role as mentors and administrators put them in a position where they have to always balance the creative expression of students to the backdrop of school policies. This gatekeeping function, although at times seen as restrictive, ensures that publications do not deviate from the guidelines of the institution, and that students are not subject to possible consequences, whilst still giving them the freedom to express their ideas. The role of advisers in navigating these tensions highlights the importance of giving advisers access to professional development opportunities to effectively balance these responsibilities.

Previous research shows the importance of advisers in student journalism as they can mentor and manage the editorial process (Espadero, 2022; Cubillas & Cubillas, 2021). These roles as mentors and mediators are crucial to sustain campus journalism programs, particularly in balancing student freedom and institutional expectations.

In order to help advisers fulfill their critical role, RA 7079 must contain provisions for professional development that address digital media skills, editorial independence, and the complexities of balancing student autonomy and institutional policies. Additionally, educational institutions should offer clearer guidelines and resources to

help advisers navigate the increasing demands of modern campus journalism, ensuring both the sustainability of the programs and the ethical training of student journalists.

Uneven Resources, Uneven Opportunities

The move to digital-first journalism has exposed large gaps in the resources available for campus journalism programs at different schools. While some schools have access to modern tools such as laptops, cameras, and internet access, others are severely limited in their access to these basic resources, which in turn limits their ability to engage fully with digital platforms. These discrepancies in resources result in unequal opportunities for students, particularly in schools that have less financial or institutional support and inhibit their capacity to produce high-quality content or acquire the necessary skills for pursuing future media careers. The fact that technology is not always available to students at many schools means some schools are using makeshift solutions, such as renting equipment or relying on the support of their peers. Despite some of these obstacles, however, the impetus to publish and the importance of student journalism continue, with quality and scope of output impacted by available resources.

- “Some schools have everything—computers, cameras, and a stable internet. We had to rent equipment with our own allowance.” (Abby, Student, School 2)
- “In my school, students have to rely on the resources we can gather from local sponsors or contests. Otherwise, we don’t have much to work with.” (Ben, School Administrator, School 5)

- “We didn’t have the equipment to publish regularly, so we used whatever we could get our hands on—borrowed computers, printers, anything.” (John, Student, School 3)
- “We’re fortunate to have the resources we do. Other schools struggle just to get basic equipment, let alone advanced tools for digital journalism.” (Ma’am Junnie, Adviser, School 4)
- “The lack of proper resources means we can’t even do online publishing. It’s limiting for students who want to learn multimedia journalism.” (Marco, Adviser, School 1)

The available data show a definitive and straightforward division exists in terms of resources for journalism on campus, with one school being able to afford the use of up-to-date technology and other schools struggling with basic infrastructure. The need for borrowed or rented equipment only underscores influence on access and puts students in under-resourced schools at a disadvantage when it comes to learning and practicing digital journalism skills. This inequality not only restricts the quality of content produced but also affects the educational experience of students, who are unable to engage fully in using modern tools of journalism. For many, this translates into not learning key skills such as video editing, layout and design, and social media management, which are essential in building a career in the field of digital media. Despite these challenges, student journalists have been showing resilience, often relying on informal networks such as alumni or other students to make up for the training gap.

The unequal distribution of resources allows a situation where opportunities are very different for students depending on what school they are in. While there are some schools that can provide a detailed digital journalism curriculum with state-of-the-art

equipment, there are also some schools that suffer financial and logistical constraints. This pattern raises the question that disparities in resources are not just forms of inconvenience, but rather first-order impediments to providing equal opportunities for navigating campus journalism in the digital age. Schools lacking access to technology and digital media may not be able to adequately prepare students for careers in modern media; they will be left behind by their peers who study in more resource-rich institutions.

Studies have found that gaps in access to technological and material resources that are common in educational settings are schools in underfunded districts that are more challenged in implementing modern media practices (Espadero, 2022; Cubillas & Cubillas, 2021). These resource gaps may prevent those students from being able to engage with the digital platforms as fully as possible and may prevent them from becoming well-rounded journalists in a digital world.

To address these prejudices, RA 7079 should include provisions for equitable distribution of resources, making sure that all schools have access to the basic tools needed to engage with digital journalism. Educational institutions and policymakers would need to focus on investing in digital infrastructure to ensure equal opportunities for all of their students to build the necessary skills for modern journalism, regardless of the financial ability of their school.

Voice as Power, Agency in Practice

Campus journalism offers a platform for self-expression for students, enabling them to cultivate critical thinking and leadership skills that enable them to function both in an academic and a personal context. As part of this work, students see their

participation in journalism as a way for them to be empowered, because they can play an active role in the content they produce and be engaged in meaningful communication on issues that affect their communities. The potential for such students to voice opinions and raise awareness about social and school-related issues has been especially important in improving student's sense of agency. Through their participation in writing, editing, and publishing, students feel like they are not only learning a journalistic skill, but they are also standing up for something. However, despite these empowering experiences, there is an underlying challenge of balancing this empowerment with institutional constraints and practical limitations of resources.

- “Being part of the school paper gives us the chance to speak out, and that makes us feel more involved in the issues that matter to us.” (Ryan, Student, School 1)
- “It has helped me become more confident in expressing my ideas, and I’ve learned how to engage with people on different issues.” (Abby, Student, School 2)
- “We get to raise awareness on topics that are usually ignored by other school organizations. That’s real power for us.” (Kyle, Student, School 3)
- “It gives students a voice in a way they might not otherwise have in the classroom or in other school activities.” (Ma’am Junnie, Adviser, School 4)
- “Even though we’re guided by the rules, being able to write articles that others read and discuss feels like we’re making a real impact.” (John, Student, School 2)

The data showed that student involvement in campus journalism gives them a sense of empowerment, especially in giving their opinion on a public platform. They consistently describe their work as more than merely an academic requirement, but rather a way to contribute meaningfully to conversations on important issues. This is a recognition of an increasing need for students to not only interact within their immediate school setting, but also to raise their voices in discussing broader societal topics. The process of writing, editing, and publishing becomes a means of expression for the student to potentially influence their peers and their community, encouraging a deep sense of agency. Despite this empowerment, students also recognize the limits they face, such as limited resources and institutional restrictions, that sometimes limit their ability to fully explore and express their ideas.

While students are empowered because they are influencing how school discussions are going, they are cognizant of the boundaries set by the school administration and the limitations of the resources available. This represents a more general tension between student autonomy and the structures in which they function. As a result, while campus journalism is used as a tool for self-expression and advocacy, students' experiences are distributed between their desire for creative freedom and the guidelines assigned by the institution. These challenges suggest the need for additional institutional support and more clarity in policies that would help enable students to capitalize on their full journalistic potential.

Research on student journalism has mentioned the role of campus journalism in promoting student empowerment, especially with the development of critical thinking and communication skills (Del Rosario, 2021; Serafica, 2013). Research has shown that when students are given platforms for expression, there is a greater

chance of them engaging with their communities and developing a strong sense of agency (Lidsky, 2016; Teer-Tomaselli, 2018).

To further help empower students, RA 7079 should contain provisions that allow for more flexibility with the student's right to express themselves, especially in the realm of digital media and social platforms. Educational institutions should also be made to offer more resources and training so students can fully develop their journalistic abilities and be involved in a meaningful way with their school and the community at large.

Balancing Time, Juggling Demands

Striking a balance between writing and publishing content while juggling extracurricular obligations can be stressful and time-consuming. While students appreciate the experience of doing journalism and consider it a way of developing themselves, they often experience difficulty with meeting deadlines and preserving academic performance. In addition, time management tends to be more challenging when they are in high publishing times (for example, with the preparation for competitions or coverage of major events at school). Indeed, in spite of these challenges, students offer a sense of loyalty to their tasks that suggest that the rewards of campus journalism (i.e., professional skills development and self-sense development) outweigh the challenge of these responsibilities.

- “It’s hard to balance writing and schoolwork. I sometimes miss assignments because we’re too focused on the next issue.” (Abby, Student, School 2)
- “The pressure is real. We have to write, edit, and then get everything done while still studying for exams.” (Kyle, Student, School 3)

- “I try to manage both, but there are times when the school paper becomes my priority. I end up pulling all-nighters to finish my homework.” (John, Student, School 1)
- “Balancing academic work with journalism tasks is stressful, but it's rewarding. I've learned how to organize my time better, even if it means sacrificing sleep.” (Ryan, Student, School 2)
- “During competitions, it's especially hard. You're not only preparing for the next issue but also studying for finals. It feels like everything's piling up at once.” (Ma'am Junnie, Adviser, School 4)

The data supports that the students who engage in campus journalism have time management anxiety especially during periods of high demand such as publication deadlines or competition seasons. Students themselves are made to play various roles - journalists, students, and at times heads in other school activities, resulting in overload. Often, the struggle to balance these responsibilities leads to late nights and poor academic performance, especially in courses that overlap with journalism work. This north-south conflict encapsulates a larger struggle from students in extracurricular activities, in that their passion for what they do may come at the expense of forgetting to do their schoolwork. Despite these challenges, interest in campus journalism remains, indicating that students see the personal and professional development afforded by their participation in campus journalism.

Students' accounts suggest that there needs to be improved institutional support, including resource support and understanding from teachers. It can clearly be seen that although students manage to juggle their journalistic responsibilities, they are still very stressed while trying to balance their academic responsibilities. These

findings highlight the need to identify ways of reducing some of these pressures, either by offering extra support during periods of peak demand or by encouraging better communication between students and teachers regarding their extracurricular activities. This more supportive framework might allow students to continue reaping the benefits of their work for campus journalism, without putting their academic success at risk.

Regarding the time management issues of the students in extra-curricular activities, some studies have emphasized the particular case of campus journalism as one of the areas where students are faced with making a choice among variety of tasks (Nassar, 2025; Del Rosario, 2021). Studies have shown that good time management techniques can decrease the levels of stress and make a person perform better not only in academic studies but also in other activities (Gulzar, 2022).

RA 7079 should have clauses pertaining to academic accommodations, so that students who are engaged in journalism do have ways to better manage their workloads without affecting their academic performance. This leads to the conclusion that in cases of high demand on the part of the student's religious duty, educational institutions should think about flexible schedules or additional assistance for students so that they can be successful not only in their studies but also in their duties as journalists.

Views on the Relevance of the Campus Journalism Act of 1991 in the Digital Age

This section highlights the insights that emerged from interviews with various stakeholders. It focuses on their views regarding the relevance of the Campus

Journalism Act of 1991, as well as their suggestions for revising the law to better meet the needs of modern and future media practices.

Outdated Act but Still Symbolic

The Campus Journalism Act of 1991 is still the foundation of student press freedom in the Philippines today, even though its stipulations have started to be considered antiquated in this age of digital media. Arguably, all sides of this debate—the school authorities, the advisers, and the students themselves—recognize the symbolic nature of the law, which encourages student expression, civic participation, and journalism development. However, with the coming of new media, online publishing, and other changes in the media landscape, the law has become less effective at guiding the current practice of campus media. While the law is an important starting place for student press freedom, it does not provide the necessary updates to accommodate the growing relevance of digital platforms for student publications. There is a growing consensus that, despite the law's continuing ability to inspire students and confirm their rights, the law is out of sync with the realities of contemporary media.

- “The law is still there to protect us, but it doesn’t really cover what we do online.”
(Ryan, Student, School 1)
- “We rely on the law for legitimacy, but its relevance is questioned when we deal with online platforms.” (Ma’am Junnie, Adviser, School 3)
- “It gives us a chance to speak up, but in today’s world, we need more guidance on digital publishing.” (Abby, Student, School 2)

- “The law is outdated. It doesn’t address the role of social media and digital tools in modern journalism.” (Ma’am May, Adviser, School 4)
- “It’s good for print, but we need a law that supports online journalism as well.” (Ben, School Administrator, School 5)

Based on the data collected, it was concluded that despite the Campus Journalism Act of 1991 still being considered as an important legal framework, it is still considered inadequate to meet the needs of the contemporary student journalists. The original orientation of the law to the medium of print does not capture the huge relevance of digital media and online platforms for journalism. Administrators and advisers pointed out the fact that the law, while providing very important protection for student journalists, does not go far enough in dealing with the changes in technology that have transformed the landscape of the media. Digital publishing, social media journalism, and online ethics are at home in the digital age. But the law has no clear provisions regarding these issues. Students have no clear framework to understand the changing landscape of journalism.

This theme highlights the tension between the symbolic significance of the law and its failure to address the practical threats that student journalists in a digital environment face. The antiquated nature of the legislation, especially in respect of its silence on digital platforms, was identified as a hindrance to effective journalistic practice in schools. Although it continues to be an important tool in protecting student press freedom, it disconnects from the current media landscape and is a developing concern. There is an obvious need for reform of the law in order to render it relevant and effective for modern digital journalism in order to bridge the gap between the original purpose of the law and the current media landscape.

Analogous to past investigations, the constraints of the Campus Journalism Act in seeing modern media practices with respect to its focus on print media journalism while also neglecting to make provisions for digital media have been identified (Arao, 2013; Dasoy, 2022). These gaps have been made even more obvious by the increasing role digital platforms play in journalism education and the need for legal reform to align with the evolving media environment.

To fund those proposed research institutional activities, RA 7079 must be amended to include provisions for digital journalism and online publishing and the ethical uses of new technologies like social media and artificial intelligence. Bringing the legislation up to date will help ensure that it continues to be effective in the future and is responsive to the challenges and opportunities posed by digital media, whilst continuing to be protective of student press freedom.

The Challenge to the Calls of Modernization

There is a loud and pervasive call from school heads, advisers, and student journalists for the modernization of the Campus Journalism Act of 1991, to align with the realities of digital media today. While the law is still widely appreciated for safeguarding student press freedom, the provisions are increasingly viewed as insufficient in light of the developments in journalism brought on by the digital revolution. Stakeholders had a strong emphasis on updates providing clear guidelines for digital publishing, ethical use of online platforms and the integration of new technologies such as artificial intelligence. This need for modernization is due to the increased use of digital tools in campus journalism that are not covered by the current normative system. It is the conclusion that unless legislative changes occur, student

journalism programs will continue to be hamstrung in both preparing students for a career in digital media, and in assuring their work meets contemporary ethical norms.

- “The law should address how we use AI in journalism. Right now, there’s no guidance on how to use these tools responsibly.” (Abby, Student, School 2)
- “It’s clear the law needs to be updated, especially when we look at what’s happening online. It’s not enough to just say ‘freedom of the press.’” (Ma’am Junnie, Adviser, School 3)
- “We need a law that includes provisions for digital platforms, online publishing, and social media.” (Sir Coco, School Administrator, School 4)
- “The law was made for print, but students today are mostly online. It’s time to make it more relevant.” (Ma’am May, Adviser, School 4)
- “We need to include provisions for online safety, digital censorship, and the responsible use of technologies like AI in the law.” (Ryan, Student, School 1)

The data showed a clear, collective recognition that the current version of the Campus Journalism Act (CJA) does not address the needs of the contemporary student journalists and their use of digital media in particular. And stakeholders representing all key actors, including students, advisers, and even school leaders, have shown there is a pressing need for reforms to the law with provisions to accommodate growing digital publishing, social media, and ethical considerations of new technologies such as AI. Students are left unguided without knowing the legal and ethical expectations around online journalism, especially topics such as content moderation, online harassment, and ethical use of AI tools. The gap between the original language of the law, which is designed for print journalism, and the

actualization of the act shows a growing disconnect between our legal concepts and the reality of today's media.

Furthermore, the request for modernization not only relates to technological upgrade but also includes ethical and legal protection of digital journalism. While participants agreed that the law is still a symbolic representation of student press rights, they also agreed that the law is insufficient in guiding students' practical abilities when it does not address the challenges of contemporary media. This gap has exposed student journalists to the threat of online censorship and ethical challenges in the online world, and without a framework of law to reference and inform their online activities. Technological progress: Modernizing the law is believed to be necessary in order for students to be well equipped to compete in the fast-changing world of digital journalism.

The rapid digitalization of journalism has been cited by some scholars as a reason to revamp media-related legislations, saying that the absence of legal frameworks for digital media puts student journalists at a disadvantage (Arao, 2013; Dasoy, 2022). Updating the law to the needs of digital journalism will help prepare students to deal with the ethical, legal, and practical problems of the digital age.

RA 7079 should be amended to cover digital media, social media journalism, and ethical use of new technologies such as AI. This will guarantee that student press freedom remains the explicit protection of the law but will also provide the necessary framework for the students to go online in a responsible way with digital tools and platforms on which they have to do press work.

Legislative Gaps in Protecting Student Journalists

Whereas the Campus Journalism Act of 1991 is meant to protect student press freedom, the law fails to fully protect student journalists, especially in the digital age. "Students, advisers and school heads consistently explained that the provisions of the law are outdated, particularly with regard to online platforms, digital censorship and the ethical use of technologies, such as artificial intelligence. The absence of specific guidelines about how to respond to digital media leave students vulnerable to online harassment, censorship, and ethical dilemmas not resolved by the law. Although the law still serves as symbolic protection of student journalism, it constitutes an inadequate means of practical protection in today's media environment. This legislative void not only impacts on the rights of student journalists but also impedes their ability to fully engage in modern journalistic practices.

- "The law doesn't protect us when it comes to online publishing or dealing with digital censorship." (Abby, Student, School 2)
- "We're mostly left on our own when it comes to handling online issues like cyberbullying or censorship." (John, Student, School 1)
- "There's nothing in the law about protecting us from online harassment. It's all about print media." (Ryan, Student, School 1)
- "The law needs to be updated. Online platforms have their own set of rules that we have to follow, and sometimes they contradict the freedom we're supposed to have." (Ma'am Junnie, Adviser, School 4)

- “We need clearer protections for students working with digital media. The current law doesn’t address these modern realities.” (Sir Coco, School Administrator, School 5)

These data indicated that there is a clear consensus among the participants that the Campus Journalism Act of 1991 fails to give student journalists the protection they require in today's digital age. Students said they were not given protection against digital censorship, online harassment, and the challenges of working with digital media, which is at the heart of contemporary journalism. This raises the question of whether the law, which is important in facilitating freedom of expression in the traditional media, has been able to adapt to journalism moving into the digital domain. Without a set of legal precedents for handling these issues, students are left unprotected against the dangers that come with publishing on the Internet and social networking. Lack of such provisions detracts from the very freedom the law is intended to defend, making the Campus Journalism Act ineffective in the contemporary global media landscape.

The chasm between the law's orientation towards print media and the reality of today's largely digital environment underscores the need for a comprehensive reform of the law. With little or no legal safeguards for digital media activities, student journalists are still vulnerable to online dangers and organizational pressures that can compromise their rights. The absence of legal clarity in dealing with issues such as digital censorship, online harassment, and appropriate use of new technologies creates a huge burden for students as they must make sense of them without the support of institutions or the law. Filling these gaps is essential to the survival of student journalism as a vibrant platform of free expression in the digital age.

The growing importance of digital media in journalism education has previously been characterized as a need for modern legal frameworks to evolve in order to adequately protect student journalists from digital harms, with several studies showing that current existing laws have not been able to do so (Arao, 2013; Dasoy, 2022). The increasing significance of online platforms in student journalism, coupled with the devastation of the January 6th incident, makes it even more important for legal assurances to be updated in line with these new challenges (Stahl, 2024; Zhou, 2024).

Long needed amendments to RA 7079 are needed to ensure there are provisions safeguarding the right of student journalists in digital space including provisions for online censorship and harassment. Educational institutions must add digital media defenses to their policies, educate student journalists with legal knowledge, and ethical guidelines, in order to guide student journalists through the current media world.

Institutional Challenges in RA 7079 Implementation

While the Campus Journalism Act of 1991 is the legislative framework of student press freedom, its implementation at institutional level is fraught with factors that make it ineffective. Both school administrators, advisers, and students raised concerns that institutional support for campus journalism programs is not uniform, and that some schools do not have the proper resources, training, and buy-in to fully enforce the law's provisions. Funding for campus publications is difficult for many schools to obtain, and teachers frequently are busy adding new responsibilities and cannot fit effective counseling into their busy schedules. Furthermore, the low awareness or lack of interest among some administrators regarding the significance

and provisions of the law has resulted in low level of enforcement of student press rights. The legal state of campus journalism restricts the ability of campus-based journalism programs to flourish, and the challenges are doubly structural: economic and systemic issues impede the law from being realized to its fullest potential.

- “There’s no real push from the school administration to fund the publication. We’re left to manage it on our own, without much support.” (Sir Ben, School Administrator, School 5)
- “The advisers are overworked, and we’re not given enough time or resources to really help students grow as journalists.” (Ma’am Junnie, Adviser, School 4)
- “At my school, the administration doesn’t really prioritize campus journalism. It’s just something that happens, not something they actively support.” (Kyle, Student, School 3)
- “We rely on our own fundraising and contests to keep the publication going. The school doesn’t allocate a specific budget for it.” (Abby, Student, School 2)
- “I feel like the administration doesn’t take the law seriously. They know it exists, but they don’t seem to understand its importance for student press freedom.” (Ma’am May, Adviser, School 4)

The lack of institutional support, as shown by the collected data, is an important reason for low-quality implementation of key elements of RA 7079. Many schools with few resources struggle to maintain their campus journalism programs, relying on one-off solutions like fundraising and outside competitions to pay for the results of their publications. This reliance on the efforts of volunteers also further burdens the challenges facing students and advisers who are already thinly stretched by their

academic and extracurricular obligations. In schools where the administration does not make campus journalism a priority, student press freedom is often curtailed, and the spirit of the law goes unfulfilled. In some cases, the institutional disregard is not the result of opposition but ignorance or misunderstanding of the purpose of the law as well as the way in which journalism can best promote civic engagement.

Advisers also encounter problems of their own, especially when they work in schools that expect them to function in multiple capacities outside of journalism, for instance, teaching core subjects or running other programs at school. They do not have the capacity to offer the mentoring and professional development that students deserve because of their enormous workload. In the absence of a formalized and institutionalized support, students have no clear framework through which to develop their skills or seek meaningful interaction with the larger community through journalism. This uneven state of implementation suggests that what is needed is a more robust institutional framework for campus journalism, one with specific resources and administrative structures that support training for both students and advisers.

There is a lack of financial and administrative support in many schools, especially in providing resources, the reason being the lack of institutional support (Espadero, 2022; Cubillas & Cubillas, 2021) and this research confirms that the successful implementation of student press laws has huge reliance on institutional support and resources. The goodwill deficit between the law and its implementation on the ground is largely impacted by the priorities of the school administrations and the workload of the advisers (EC Dasoy, 2022).

These institutional challenges must be addressed, and in this regard the pertinent provisions of RA 7079 shall be amended to include specific provisions that

would provide for institutional support in terms of clear guidelines on funding and staffing, and professional growth of the advisers. Schools should be required to provide special resources for journalism programs on their campuses and to establish structures that make student press freedom an integral part of the educational process.

Views on the Integration of Digital Media in Campus Journalism Programs

This section presents the insights that emerged from the interviews with various stakeholders, focusing on their perceptions of the integration of digital media and online journalism in the curriculum of campus journalism. It also explores the specific training and resources necessary for the stakeholders.

Learning by Doing, Not by Curriculum

The use of digital media within campus journalism programs is largely unorganized, and a lot of times students are learning by doing instead of an official curriculum. Although digital tools are now ubiquitous in student journalism, schools do not offer much formal instruction in digital journalism, or the instruction is varied or inconsistently applied. Often, students have to learn digital skills on their own or seek peer and alumni assistance to develop their digital literacy skills such as social media management, graphic design, and video editing. Whilst advisers recognize the importance of digital capabilities, they are often ineffective at providing formal, in-depth training. This use of informal, experiential learning highlights a serious gap in the

curriculum, since many schools do not effectively incorporate digital journalism into the sphere of formal education.

- “We learned digital tools by doing them ourselves—there was no real curriculum for it.” (Kyle, Student, School 1)
- “Training in digital journalism was brief, we mostly had to figure things out as we went.” (Jenna, Student, School 2)
- “We get help from SPJ graduates... it’s like a loop that goes on.” (Ryan, Student, School 2)
- “Our adviser is good, but digital tools like layouting and video editing were things we mostly taught ourselves.” (Abby, Student, School 3)
- “There are a lot of digital skills I wish I had learned formally, but we mostly learn them from alumni or by experimenting.” (John, Student, School 1)

Based on these empirical findings students in campus journalism education were predominantly using self-guided learning and/or an informal rather than a formal curriculum. This is especially true in resource-challenged schools, where advisers cannot invest hours in training students on digital tools and are left with the students figuring things out on their own or by learning from fellow students and alumni. Whilst this unstructured learning helps to develop independence and problem-solving skills, there is a gap in the acquisition of formal learning, which could lead to students being underprepared for professional careers in digital journalism. The use of informal training networks, including alumni and peer trainings, underscores the need for systemic reform in the way digital skills are taught within the campus journalism program.

Despite these challenges, the experiential, hands-on learning model undertaken by students has proven to be effective in developing certain skill sets such as adaptability, creativity and resourcefulness. However, this is an inconsistent approach and students with less access to experienced mentors, or digital materials are at separate disadvantage. Second, without formal curriculum integration for digital media available in the journalism curriculum, opportunities for skill acquisition are not available equally to all students, which further widens the gap between students at well-resourced institutions and students at less well-resourced institutions.

It has been documented that many journalism programs do not have digital media training in their curricula (Hossain, Wenger, & Senseman, 2024) and multi-media skills are usually left to be acquired by students through informal networks or independently. The lack of an organized curriculum for digital journalism is a documented gap in education, particularly considering how digital tools have become a key part of practice for modern journalism (Schmidt, 2020).

To bridge this gap, RA 7079 must contain provisions for the formal integration of digital journalism in the curriculum, such that all students will be able to access formal training on basic digital skills. The urgency is on educational institutions to inform their curriculum to incorporate the digital media tools and techniques, to ensure that students are capable of mastering the skills necessary to compete in this ever-changing media environment and the need to ensure transfer of skills among student journalists before they leave the school and pursue higher education.

AI Tools, Experimental Approaches

The use of artificial intelligence (AI) models such as ChatGPT in campus journalism has emerged as a pragmatic, if unregulated, solution to content creation. While the use of AI tools has been welcomed by some students to aid the brainstorming, writing, and structuring of articles, the reliance on AI occurs without formal instruction on how to use it ethically and with limitations. While AI is becoming an increasingly popular tool among students to boost their productivity and creativity, there are currently no explicit policies or curriculum integration in place, which means students are learning how to use these tools on their own. AI tools are potentially problematic in ethical terms around authorship and plagiarism, with students possibly becoming too dependent on AI technologies without fully realizing the implications of their use. This trend represents the increasing integration of AI into journalism, but it also underscores the need for established guidelines and structured training on ethical concerns and best practices in utilizing these tools.

- “I use ChatGPT to help me brainstorm ideas and structure articles. It’s fast, but I always double-check the content.” (Ryan, Student, School 1)
- “AI is useful, but there’s a lot of grey area on how much we can rely on it for content creation.” (Marco, Adviser, School 1)
- “I’ve started using ChatGPT for writing. It saves a lot of time, but I know I have to make sure it’s accurate.” (Abby, Student, School 2)
- “Sometimes we use AI to come up with article ideas, but I think it’s important to use it wisely and not let it do everything.” (Kyle, Student, School 3)

- “AI tools are helpful, but there’s no clear guideline for how to use them properly. We just figure it out as we go.” (John, Student, School 2)

With data indicating widespread use of AI tools, especially ChatGPT by the students to aid in different areas of campus journalism from idea generation to article drafting. However, despite the usefulness of these tools students also express a keen awareness of the potential teething problems that accompany this technology such as the risk that AI-generated content is used inappropriately or excessively. This uncontrolled application of AI is yet another instance of a massive gap in the curriculum, where students are left to stumble through these technologies without a strong ethical framework to guide them or structured academic training to learn about them. Using AI for writing, brainstorming, and even content organization would imply that students are looking for ways to maximize their productivity for a world that's moving at an ever-faster digital pace, but the lack of formal guidance may result in unintended side effects such as problems of plagiarism and loss of authorship.

The lack of formal education on the use of an AI is also representative of trend on campuses where, often, technological improvements are adopted on an ad-hoc basis rather than through intentional education structures. The ethical issues surrounding AI—the authorship, accuracy and accountability of what is being published—are largely left out of the discussion, leaving the responsibility for learning them up to the students. Without clear guidelines or policies in place, students risk using AI tools in ways that they may not understand or intend, which could have long-term consequences for their journalistic integrity and skill development.

The integration of AI into journalism is an increasing concern in the academic and professional world, with some academics highlighting the importance of ethical

frameworks to support the use of AI in content creation (Zhou, 2024; Stahl, 2024). These concerns are reminiscent of the difficulties students face in campus journalism, who are using AI tools without support or examples.

Finally, to address the ethical issues surrounding the use of AI in campus journalism, RA 7079 should be amended to include provisions that will apply to the use of digital tools, such as AI, and produce ethical standards for their use in student publications. In order to ensure that students can use these tools effectively but also understand the ethical considerations that surround using them in journalism, higher education institutions must also make AI literacy a part of the curriculum.

Digital Literacy as a Core Skill for Student Journalists

Digital literacy has become an important means of expression for student journalists, but its application to campus journalism programs has proven inconsistent. While both students and advisers acknowledge the need for digital tools in contemporary journalism, due to the lack of explicit training in digital media skills in the formal curriculum. Many students are left on their own to learn or informally learn to use digital tools like social media management skills, graphic design, and video editing. This lack of formal training represents a larger issue in campus journalism programs with a critical lack of digital skills education. Consequently, they may not be well-equipped to meet the challenges of modern journalism and are unable to use digital platforms to their utmost potential.

- “We rely on YouTube tutorials and alumni workshops to learn things like graphic design and video editing. There’s no official training.” (Abby, Student, School 2)

- “We try to teach digital literacy, but it’s not structured. Some students are more comfortable with technology, and some are not.” (Ma’am Junnie, Adviser, School 4)
- “In the journalism club, we’ve had to figure out how to use social media and design apps on our own. It’s a trial-and-error process.” (Kyle, Student, School 3)
- “Digital tools like Canva and Adobe are crucial for our work, but we don’t have formal lessons on how to use them properly.” (Ryan, Student, School 1)
- “Our curriculum focuses more on writing and reporting. Digital literacy should be a core part of the training, but it’s not prioritized.” (Ma’am May, Adviser, School 4)

The data shows that digital literacy, while seen as a key component of journalism in the modern campus, is unevenly and informally incorporated into the curriculum. Other essential skills like graphic design, social media management, and video editing are generally left for students to figure out on their own through peer workshops or online tutorials. This lack of future preparation for students is but one example of the gap in digital journalism education for school students. While some people can self-instigate the skills needed to develop these skills, others, especially those with fewer resources available or digital skills, are left behind. This digital literacy gap undercuts all students’ ability to maximally leverage the tools needed for successful journalism in the digital age.

The use of informal learning paths, such as the development of self-taught skills using online resources or the advice of alumni, uncovers the lack of a formal structure

for DL that exists in campus journalism programs. This disparity in access leaves some students more highly proficient than others, which in turn, creates gaps and inequities between those students who have had exposure to digital tools and those who have not. In addition, without proper training or integration of the curriculum, students may not fully understand the ethical implications or advanced strategies required to navigate the digital media landscape successfully. Thus, without institutionalized digital literacy training, not only does it compromise students' technical capabilities, but digital publishing and social media use can also become devoid of ethical responsibilities.

Academics are clear that digital literacy is necessary for students who aim to work in journalism, especially within the context of an increasingly digital first world news (Schmidt 2020; Hossain, Wenger, & Senseman 2024). In the context of formal digital media education, a scarcity of skills may prevent students from being adequately trained for pursuing modern journalism, further the importance of when considering education in structured learning experiences of digital tools and platforms (Buckingham, 2019).

RA 7079 should also be amended to incorporate well-defined digital literacy education provisions that will enable all students to be literate and to teach and learn in this digital media environment. Digital literacy should be a key component of journalism curriculum at these institutions, giving students and advisers the resources and training to use this new medium successfully.

Digital Tools as Enablers of Collaboration

Digital tools have been instrumental to the development of collaboration amongst student journalists, allowing them to work together more effectively in diverse types of work, from writing to editing to selecting content. While students and advisers know the value of digital platforms in facilitating improved teamwork, the extent of teamwork varies according to the school's access to technology and the students' familiarity with digital tools. Platforms such as Google Docs, social media, and online collaboration tools have made it possible to get feedback and communicate in real-time with the school, making it easier for students to share ideas and materials.

- “We use Google Docs to write together, and it’s much easier to track changes and make sure everyone is on the same page.” (Abby, Student, School 2)
- “Social media platforms help us get immediate feedback from readers and even the school community. It’s a great way to engage and collaborate.” (Kyle, Student, School 3)
- “I feel that digital tools like shared drives and collaborative apps make working as a team so much smoother. We can contribute to the article from different places at the same time.” (Ryan, Student, School 1)
- “We often use online tools to stay in touch when we’re not physically at school. This helps us keep the publication on track, even with busy schedules.” (Ma’am Junnie, Adviser, School 4)
- “Even though we have the tools, we don’t always know how to use them effectively. Sometimes we figure it out as we go.” (John, Student, School 1)

The data reveals that digital tools are key towards facilitating collaboration between student journalists, enabling real-time communication, collaborative content production and feedback. These tools, especially cloud-based programs such as Google Docs and social media, have made it much easier for students to collaborate with each other because they can work in asynchronously, even when they are not physically in the same space. The capacity for sharing documents, tracking changes and conversation over mediums such as social media has increased how students generate content as a team, widening the scope of teamwork beyond traditional face-to-face interactions. Despite these advantages, however, the lack of formal training in the use of these digital tools limits the ability for students to reach their full potential as they often rely on trial and error or peer support on figuring out how to use them effectively.

This pattern then suggests that while digital tools have certainly changed the collaborative process in campus journalism, their implementation has left an important gap in training. Many students, despite their enthusiasm and initiative, are left to navigate these tools with little to no support and therefore, may lose out on using them to the greatest benefit, or may face inefficiencies and lose out on the more sophisticated forms of collaboration they have to offer. The lack of structured guidance on how to use these digital platforms means that students are not really equipped to take advantage of the collaborative potential of these tools, limiting the quality and scope of their work. To get the most out of these tools, schools must make the use of digital media an integral part of the journalism curriculum, in order to make sure students know how to effectively use these platforms and do so confidently.

Learning about, producing, and utilizing digital collaboration tools has become more recognized than ever before in journalism education because students communicate and collaborate more effectively with the tools (Buckingham, 2019; Schmidt, 2020). The use of these tools enables students to navigate geographical and time bound gaps thus improving the efficiency and quality of collaborative work in journalism (Gulzar, 2022).

To facilitate the proper utilization of digital tools in campus journalism, the provisions of RA 7079 should address the promotion of digital literacy as well as integration of digital collaboration tools in the curriculum. Educational institutions should focus on professional development for both students and advisers, ensuring that they have the necessary skills to effectively use digital platforms for collaboration and content creation.

Ethical Dilemmas in Digital Journalism

As digital tools have become more integrated into campus journalism, ethical dilemmas about the responsible use of these platforms have arisen as a result. Students and advisers said they are struggling with issues such as plagiarism, authorship, online harassment and accuracy of information, which are enhanced in digital media environments. Despite the excitement of students in the use of digital tools, there is a lack of formal instruction on ethical practices in digital journalism and students then have to figure to do this all alone. Many students admitted to using AI tools, social media, and other online platforms without having a full grasp of the ethical implications, such as the potential for misinformation or misattribution. The lack of a clear ethical framework in the curriculum or in the law has led to a situation in which

students are left to resolve these dilemmas independently, which could lead to inconsistent practices and potential violations of journalistic integrity.

- “We use AI to help us write and brainstorm ideas, but I’m not sure how much of it is okay to use without changing it.” (Ryan, Student, School 1)
- “Sometimes we just pick up news from social media and use it without verifying if it's accurate. It's hard to know what counts as plagiarism online.” (Abby, Student, School 2)
- “I’ve had to deal with comments and messages criticizing our content. It feels like online harassment, but we don’t really know how to handle it.” (Kyle, Student, School 3)
- “We talk about being ethical in journalism, but it’s mostly about print media. When it comes to online platforms, the rules aren’t as clear.” (Ma’am Junnie, Adviser, School 4)
- “Sometimes, we take inspiration from other articles or social media, but we don’t always properly cite sources. There’s no clear rule on that for digital media.” (John, Student, School 1)

The data reveals that students in campus journalism are facing new ethical challenges as they make a shift from the traditional media of print to the new media of digital. Problems such as plagiarism, authorship, and AI tools used without understanding fully of the ethical implications become an increasing issue. The dependence on social media as a source of information and the accessibility of copying and pasting information online have blurred the lines of what ethical journalism is. Without any formal guidelines on ethics specific to digital journalism, students are

left to self-regulate or learn from the experiences of peers, which can result in inconsistent practices and confusion about what is acceptable. This lack of clear direction from the curriculum or institutional policies is indicative of a larger gap in the way that ethical journalism is taught in the digital age.

Moreover, a lack of anything formal specifying the rules of engagement of online harassment and content verification makes the difficulties faced by students involved in digital journalism all the more insufferable. While students know they have to report responsibly, the nuances of online ethics -- including addressing misinformation, plagiarism and digital harassment -- are less well-understood. According to the data, while students are excited about using digital tools, there is often a lack of the ethical framework needed to effectively navigate these tools and as a result, the unintended consequences of violating journalistic standards can ensue. This gap points to a need for more comprehensive training and clearer ethical guidelines in the curriculum in order to prepare students for the complexities of digital journalism.

Research on digital journalism ethics highlight how the quickly growing use of digital media has introduced new challenges in upholding the principles of journalistic integrity, especially when it comes to matters such as plagiarism, misinformation and online harassment (Stahl, 2024; Zhou, 2024). Research has suggested that formalized training in digital ethics is necessary to give students the knowledge and skills necessary to navigate through these new dilemmas (Schmidt, 2020).

RA 7079 should be amended to include clear guidelines on the ethics of digital journalism, including issues such as plagiarism, misinformation, and online harassment. Educational institutions need to make digital ethics a part of the

journalism curriculum, so that students are not only learning how to use digital tools but also becoming aware of the ethical responsibilities that come with them.

Table 1. Theme Summary Table

The table shows the summary of the themes identified in the results. It contains the themes, the core ideas from the statements of the participants, the stakeholders that are most affected, and the direct statements from them.

Theme	Core Idea	Stakeholders Most Affected	Sample Quote (ID)
Digital-first by Necessity, not by Design	Shift to online-first publishing due to resource constraints; increased reach but added editorial demands	Students, Advisers, School Heads	“We publish online now—no more printed issues...” (Jenna, S2)
Advisers as Mentors and Mediators	Advisers balance student autonomy with institutional policies; central to the sustainability of journalism programs	Advisers, School Heads	“We’re not just writing and meeting deadlines; we’re also making sure students don’t overstep boundaries set by the administration.” (Marco, S1)
Uneven resources, uneven opportunities	Disparities in digital resources create unequal opportunities for students, affecting	Students, Advisers, School Heads	“Some schools have everything—computers, cameras, and stable internet. We had to rent

	quality and engagement		equipment with our own allowance.” (Abby, S2)
Voice as Power, Agency in Practice	RA 7079 remains a foundational framework but is outdated in the context of modern digital media	Students, Advisers, School Heads	“The law is still there to protect us, but it doesn’t really cover what we do online.” (Ryan, S1)
Challenges of Time Management and Academic Balance	The demands of campus journalism conflict with academic responsibilities, leading to time management struggles	Students	“It’s hard to balance writing and schoolwork. I sometimes miss assignments because we’re too focused on the next issue.” (Abby, S2)
Outdated Act but Still Symbolic	While the Act remains foundational symbol for press freedom, its provisions do not address realities of the modern media	Students, Advisers, School Heads	“The law is still there to protect us, but it doesn’t really cover what we do online.” (Ryan, S1)
The Challenge to the Call for Modernization	The need to update RA 7079 to address digital media, AI tools, and ethical guidelines	Students, Advisers, School Heads	“The law should address how we use AI in journalism. Right now, there’s no guidance on how to use these tools responsibly.” (Abby, S2)
Legislative Gaps in Protecting Student Journalists	RA 7079 fails to address modern challenges in digital journalism, such as online	Students, Advisers, School Heads	“The law doesn’t protect us when it comes to online publishing or dealing with

	harassment and digital censorship		digital censorship.” (Abby, S2)
Institutional Challenges in RA 7079 Implementation	Lack of resources, administrative support, and awareness hinder the effective implementation of RA 7079	Students, Advisers, School Heads	“There’s no real push from the school administration to fund the publication. We’re left to manage it on our own.” (Ben, School Head, S5)
Learning by doing, not by curriculum	Students learn digital journalism through informal, hands-on methods rather than formal training in the curriculum	Students	“We learned digital tools by doing them ourselves—there was no real curriculum for it.” (Kyle, S1)
AI Tools, Experimental Approaches	Students use AI tools like ChatGPT for content creation, raising ethical concerns regarding authorship and plagiarism	Students, Advisers	“I use ChatGPT to help me brainstorm ideas and structure articles. It’s fast, but I always double-check the content.” (Ryan, S1)
Digital Literacy as a Core Skill for Student Journalists	Digital literacy is essential for student journalists, but its integration into the curriculum is inconsistent	Students, Advisers	“We rely on YouTube tutorials and alumni workshops to learn things like graphic design and video editing. There’s no official training.” (Abby, S2)

Digital Tools as Enablers of Collaboration

Digital tools enhance collaboration among students, allowing for real-time feedback and content creation across locations

Students, Advisers

“We use Google Docs to write together, and it’s much easier to track changes and make sure everyone is on the same page.”
(Abby, S2)

Ethical Dilemmas in Digital Journalism

Ethical challenges arise in digital journalism, particularly concerning plagiarism, AI usage, and online harassment

Students, Advisers

“We use AI to help us write and brainstorm ideas, but I’m not sure how much of it is okay to use without changing it.” (Ryan, S1)

Chapter V

SUMMARY, CONCLUSION, AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter is the summary of the key findings of after interviewing student journalists, the advisers of the school papers as well as the administrators of schools on their perspectives and opinions on how the implementation of campus journalism is being carried on specifically in the context of new developments in technology. It also presents a description of the conclusions, which were made as a result of thematic analysis of data in regard to the research questions of the study. Lastly, the chapter provides suggestions to strengthen the journalism practice on campus, reform respective policy regulations, especially the Campus Journalism Act of 1991, and increase the inclusion of the digital media into the training of journalism. Such suggestions should prepare students better to face the realities of new media. The understanding in this paper is intended to assist the educators, school leaders, and policymakers in improving the role of campus journalism in academic and socio-civic development.

Summary

This section presents a comprehensive summary of the major findings derived from the analysis of interview data collected from student journalists, school paper advisers, and school administrators.

Stakeholder Perspectives and Legislative Reflections

The findings indicate that it has taken over student journalism with the majority of the students vacating the print media in preference of online publishing. The engagement of social media sites and AI-assistance, like ChatGPT, is becoming a prominent method of improving content production. However, despite these developments, students in some schools have found it hard to get the equipment as it has been reported that there is a disparity of resources with regard to the equipment. Despite these challenges, participation in campus journalism has positively influenced students' career paths, with many choosing to pursue journalism or related fields in college.

School Paper Advisers and student journalists also supported the relevance of digital media in campus journalism but noted the lack of resources, infrastructure and training as well. When discussing the professional training, advisers pointed to the necessity of professional education in the digital skills: layout design, video editing, and SEO, and the scarcity of funds to implement digital journalism education. The student journalists reiterated the importance of campus journalism in the empowerment and academic growth of students but also raised the lack of infrastructure at schools i.e. limited internet access. The participants also concurred that the Campus Journalism Act of 1991 must be revised in accordance with the modern age of the digital era and in relation to online publishing, digital censorship, and ethical application of AI. The research proposes streamlining the law, that resources are available to students equally, and that there be some form of professional training in order to impart skills in the students, so that they are equipped with digital media skills.

Views on the Relevance of the Campus Journalism Act of 1991 in the Digital Age

The Act was important to student journalists according to whom it will defend their freedom of expression, as well as allow them to publish without being afraid that their material will be censored. Nevertheless, they also mentioned that the current law is not taking into account the current digital journalism environment, including online publications, social forms of media and the ethical use of such emerging technologies as AI. They demanded changes to the legislation, in particular, the need to protect data online, use AI, academic accommodations, and permanent funding. Advisers echoed these sentiments saying that although the Act is still providing importance in legitimizing student journalism, it does not provide any notion of digital media and even the provisions on the Act are often unpredictable with some being inconsistently implemented due to the shortage of resources. The administrators of schools also acknowledged how the Act has helped students gain some powers, but noted that there were difficulties in its practice, namely, in terms of funding and making digital journalism a part of the curriculum. They proposed to review the law, modernize it, to cater to the existing state of digital media practices and have more evident support structures.

All in all, the results speak to the fact that as necessary and effective the Campus Journalism Act remains as a tool to protect student press freedom, other forms of law need to be developed to protect the demands of digital journalism in a contemporary world. The failure of the Act to accommodate the existence of online platforms, digitalized media, and AI technologies exposes student journalists to further causes of difficulties like cyberbullying and online censorship. There is a comprehensive demand for policy revision so that the development of media can be

aligned with the law, especially the integration of digital journalism, online safety, and sufficient funding of the campus journalism program. The paper outlines the importance of repealing the Act to reinstate its importance in securing the strength of student journalists in the digital era.

Views on the Integration of Digital Media in Campus Journalism Programs

This paper points to the increased awareness of digital media as a new norm in campus journalism. The participants observe the growing role of digital tools in making current journalism. The majority of students indicated a movement towards online publishing as opposed to print which has wider reach and an option of providing immediate publications. The social media is also an important element of student journalism in terms of posting and what they do in terms of engaging individuals in real-time publications. Whereas digital media has been regarded as a necessity, students highlighted that its incorporation into the journalism curriculum has been to a small extent. Journalism training digitally related training can be informal, and it is common that students rely on self-help or encourage one another and/or act as alumni. It becomes clear that there is a call to bring digital journalism in the curriculum in a systematic manner and to give professionals training in order to instill skills within them.

Advisers and school administrators agreed on the necessity of digital media but pointed out to the major issue of facilities and resources. Most schools cannot find the needed resources, i.e., laptops, cameras, editing programs in order to be able to properly incorporate digital journalism into their curriculum. The advisers also reported being ill equipped to advise students on the aspects of digital skills due to lack of the

technical knowledge. Although these are some of the obstacles that need to be overcome, advisers and school heads saw the potential of digital journalism to augment student engagement and increase their reach. The paper proposes a modernization of the Campus Journalism Act of 1991 to reflect the current trends of the online world of journalism, such as possibilities to publish online, online safety, and integrity of ethically acceptable use of evolving technologies. The results indicate a necessity in perceiving an enhanced policy reform, enhanced distribution of resources, and career growth to facilitate the actions of digital media in campus journalism education.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were made.

1. The findings indicate that digital media have become the dominant tools for practicing campus journalism, with the majority of students abandoning print media in favor of online publishing. Social media platforms and AI tools, like ChatGPT, have become integral to enhancing content production and engaging with audiences. However, there are significant disparities in resources, as students in some areas struggle to access essential equipment such as cameras and computers. Despite these challenges, participation in campus journalism has positively impacted students' career paths, with many opting to pursue journalism or related fields in college. Advisers and school leaders also support the relevance of digital media in campus journalism but highlighted issues like limited resources, infrastructure, and training. Both advisers and school heads agreed that the Campus Journalism Act of 1991 needs to be updated to address the digital age, particularly in areas such as online

publishing, digital censorship, and the ethical use of AI. The paper proposes reforms to streamline the law, ensure equitable access to resources, and incorporate professional training for students to equip them with necessary digital media skills.

2. The Campus Journalism Act of 1991 continues to play an important role in protecting student journalists' freedom of expression, allowing them to publish without fear of censorship. However, student journalists noted that the law does not account for the current digital journalism environment, including online platforms, social media, and the ethical use of emerging technologies like AI. They called for changes to the Act to address these issues, with a focus on online protection, academic accommodations, and sustainable funding. School paper advisers also acknowledged the Act's importance in legitimizing student journalism but pointed out that it lacks provisions for digital media, often leaving its implementation inconsistent and underfunded. School administrators recognized the empowering role of the Act in supporting student press freedom, but they raised concerns about funding and integrating digital journalism into the curriculum. The study concludes that the Act must be modernized to address the evolving needs of digital journalism, including online publishing, digital safety, and the ethical use of technology.
3. This paper highlights the growing awareness of digital media as a new norm in campus journalism. The participants acknowledge the increasing role of digital tools in modern journalism. Most students reported a shift toward online publishing due to its wider reach and immediate publication benefits, with social media playing a crucial role in engaging their audience in real-time. However, students noted that the integration of digital media into the journalism

curriculum remains limited. Training in digital journalism is often informal, with students relying on peer support or alumni-led initiatives. There is a strong call for digital journalism to be systematically incorporated into the curriculum, with professional training in digital tools such as layout programs, video editing, and social media management. The participants also agreed on the necessity of digital media but highlighted significant barriers, including the lack of resources and infrastructure. The study emphasizes the need for policy reforms to ensure that digital journalism is fully integrated into campus journalism programs, supported by adequate funding and professional development for both students and educators.

Recommendations

The results of this paper indicate that although Campus Journalism Act of 1991 (RA 7079) remains to be the cornerstone of student press freedom in the Philippines, its implementation in the schools has remained skewed and limited to a conjunction of obsolete provisions, the mediation of the administration and the burdens of advisor work and resource inequality. More so, the law has not been keeping up with the fast sea change caused by the digital media and students and advisers are guided in the new mediums without any specific institutional assistance or guidance. Concurrently, the endurance radiation of the stakeholders testifies that the field of campus journalism is a very crucial arena of empowerment and engagement although operating within limited conditions. The bigger picture which arises is visible as one both promising and constraining: campus journalism is still flourishing as a democratic practice, yet their full potential forever might be advanced by means of reforms, which involve

overcoming systemic, institutional and third person restricting factors. Based on this, the following recommendations are the following.

Lawmakers, the Department of Education (DepEd) and in the same breath the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) should re-read and amend RA 7079 to ensure that it is more in line with the realities of the digital age. Although in the past, the law has ensured the student the right to publish and speak, there is no clear-cut directives when it comes to publishing online and digital ethics as well as multimedia production. Such a wholesome overhaul must thus incorporate the element of digital journalism as a requisite skill within the school-based curriculum and as such, students must be not only taught to write and edit effectively; but through the use of digital technology, they would also be taught to be responsible and principled with everything that involves online communication. With this, the government is supposed to institutionalize mechanisms of mounting baseline funds on the publications of schools. Currently, most schools are using contests or small, occasional budgetary allocations to fund their journalism programs, which mainly worsens disparities between schools with and without financial resources. Systemic changes should be ensured at the state level, to ensure all schools can afford to operate a publication, no matter the conditions locally. It is also crucial that nationwide capacity-building initiatives among advisers and students be institutionalized with the help of cooperating with higher-learning institutions and the professional journalism associations. These programs would offer uniform training on either traditional or digital practices, which would fill the knowledge gap and skills gap as it is currently in place. Lastly, there should be clear monitoring and evaluation system in determining the organizing level of implementation of the law whether the implementation of RA 7079 is more than a mere symbolism or not and its law is effectively oriented into practical significance.

School administrators are intentional at the institutional level to develop the culture of the campus journalism programs and its sustainability. Although stipulated by RA 7079, its effectiveness is considerable when it comes to the school policies and leadership choices that must be operationalized. Schools should implement policies that actually respect the freedom of student publications, whereby administrative control effort should not suffocate journalistic freedom. Also, the process of incorporating digital journalism calls upon making tangible investments in infrastructure, i.e. recent computers, the reliable access (to internet), multimedia. These resources are essential even to the most motivated students and advisers as they will find it difficult to maintain their work. At the school level, advisers should also be given the higher priority in the line of professional development. Offering time, financing and incentives to the advisers to undergo training programs and workshops in order to provide them sufficient time, schools can ensure that they manage not only the technical aspects of the digital journalism field but are also assisted in coordinating their numerous roles. Outside resources, schools ought to also be fostering a culture of cooperation introducing to campus journalism not merely as a contest-based activity, but as a culture that involves administrators, advisers and students working together to support the purpose of continuing campus journalism. Through a positive appreciation of publications as avenues of participation and empowerment, schools may guarantee that emptiness is brought to the journalism programs through educational participation.

At the personal level, there are teachers, advisers and students themselves who may do something to perpetuate campus journalism as a democratic venue. This implies that, in addition to technical training, advisers should be provided with frameworks that deal with the same in line with digital citizenship, online ethics, and

multimedia storytelling. They are also the enablers of writing and editing as well as the shepherds who help the learners in various tasks of online journalism writing to be responsible enough. Students in turn need to internalize the need to take the chance of campus journalism as a work of civic activism and self-development. Their active social involvement in both offline and online channels can give them a better opportunity to raise their voices and at the same time fulfill the principles of accountability and ethics. Both teachers and students are supposed to establish communities of practice beyond and inside their respective schools where the peer-to-peer learning can aid in gap closing in terms of knowledge and skills. Through this, advisers and student journalists have the opportunity to learn or become co learners alongside changeable media realities.

Lastly, this paper guides towards a number of the future research may also examine actual revision of the law and lobbying it to policymakers. To begin with, similar research in other parts of the Philippines would illuminate on how the local circumstances can be able to impact the adoption of RA 7079, so the similar studies can be made in areas with a higher quantity of resources and those with fewer resources. It would be also beneficial to conduct comparative international studies since it would put the Philippine campus journalism in the context of the debates on student press freedom and digital media integration as well as providing insights on the same that can both guide the policy and the practice. The other avenue that would be worth pursuing is to explore how schools are trying to navigate the digital transitions with the particular models of innovation arising and the barriers that have been observed to emerge throughout the journey. The longitudinal research might also prove to further illuminate research by tracking the transformation of the perspectives

of student journalists and advisers with time, especially as journalism is ever-changing through digital means.

This research paper emphasizes the fact that the viability of the work on enhancing campus journalism demands a multi-level strategy: legislative interventions that will update RA 7079, institutional appeals that will provide favorable conditions, and personal actions that will preserve ethical and innovative practices. It is only via concerted effort on all these levels that campus journalism can truly be all it is dreamed of participating, empowering, and voicing in the digital era.

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Appendices

APPENDIX A

Letter of Request

03 April 2025

DR. ROSEMARIE D. TORRES, CESO V
Schools Division Superintendent
DepEd SDO Cavite Province
Trece Martires City, Cavite

Dr. Torres:

I, Carlo Jay F. Ruiz, am a Master of Development Communication (MDC) student at UP Open University. I am currently conducting research, titled "*A Phenomenological Study of Stakeholders' Experiences in Campus Journalism Implementation at Secondary Schools in Cavite,*" under the supervision of Dr. Joane V. Serrano.

The research aims to explore the lived experiences of stakeholders—student journalists, advisers, and school administrators—in secondary schools in Cavite, focusing on the implementation of campus journalism programs under the Campus Journalism Act of 1991, and to examine the need for reforms in this law to adapt to the demands of modern journalism.

With this, I am asking you to allow me to conduct interviews to my research participants including some campus journalists, School Paper Advisers, and School Heads who will be willing to be interviewed. Their participation would involve a single interview lasting approximately 60 minutes.

Their participation would significantly contribute to the validity and depth of my findings. Also, the conduct of the interview will be entirely voluntary, and participants are free to withdraw at any time without any consequences.

Shall there be any further questions, feel free to contact me via email at cf Ruiz@up.edu.ph or by phone at (+63) 975 196 2996.

I have attached a sample guide of questions for the interview.

Sin

CARLO JAY F. RUIZ
MDC Student

Noted

JOANE V. SERRANO, PhD
Research Adviser

APPENDIX B

Approved Letter to Conduct

Republic of the Philippines
Department of Education

REGION IV-A

SCHOOLS DIVISION OFFICE OF CAVITE PROVINCE

1st Indorsement

April 11, 2025

Respectfully returned to CARLO JAY F. RUIZ, researcher(s) from University of the Philippines-Open University, with the information that this Office interposes no objection to the attached request to conduct the study titled, "A PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY OF STAKEHOLDERS' EXPERIENCES AND IN CAMPUS JOURNALISM IMPLEMENTATION AT SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN CAVITE." This indorsement is provided under the condition that the following requirements shall be meticulously observed:

1. Ensure proper coordination with the school head(s) of the concerned school(s).
2. Emphasize that participation in the study is entirely voluntary, with no coercion or pressure on any participant.
3. Prior to administering the research instrument, **provide appropriate consent forms** to all target participants. Consent is a fundamental ethical requirement in all research involving human subjects.
4. If the research involves interviewing students aged 17 years or younger, secure copies of **parental consent forms and assent from the minors.**
5. Schedule research activities to take place after regular class hours to minimize disruptions to ongoing classes and school activities.
6. Conduct research activities in a manner that does not interfere with the regular functioning of the school.
7. Ensure that all data collected during the research are treated with the utmost confidentiality and privacy. Any personally identifiable information of participants must be securely stored and anonymized in all reports.
8. Submit a **hard copy of the research to the DepEd Cavite Division Library Hub** for the benefit of the researchers in the Division.

ROSEMARIE D. TORRES, CESO V
Schools Division Superintendent

----- AGREEMENT -----

I agree to submit a hard copy of my research to the Division Office for the utilization of its personnel.

CARLO JAY F. RUIZ

Signature over Printed Name

School: UP OPEN UNIVERSITY

Contact No.: (+63) 975 196 2996

Cavite Capitol Compound, Brgy. Luolano, Trece Martires City, Cavite
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APPENDIX C

Informed Consent for Participants 18 years old and above

INFORMED CONSENT FOR PARTICIPANTS 18 YEARS OLD AND ABOVE

Research Title: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY OF STAKEHOLDERS' EXPERIENCES IN CAMPUS JOURNALISM IMPLEMENTATION AT SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN CAVITE

Researcher(s): Carlo Jay F. Ruiz

School/Organization/Office: University of the Philippines-Open University

Contact Number: 09751962996

You are invited to participate in this research study. Before you decide, it is important that you know what the research is all about and why it is being done. The main purpose of this study is to explore the lived experiences of stakeholders—student journalists, advisers, and school administrators—in secondary schools in Cavite, focusing on the implementation of campus journalism programs under the Campus Journalism Act of 1991, and to examine the need for reforms in this law to adapt to the demands of modern journalism. The study will require one session of interview. It will require one hour for you to complete the session.

The benefit(s) involved in participating in this study is the opportunity for personal reflection, empowerment through sharing their voices, contribution to policy and practice improvements, enhanced networking and skill development, increased awareness of relevant issues, recognition in research outputs, and access to valuable findings that can inform their own practices and the broader community. The risk(s) involved in participating in this study are risks such as discomfort from discussing sensitive or negative experiences, concerns about confidentiality and privacy, misunderstandings regarding the study's purpose or use of their insights, possible repercussions from school administrations or peers, and the emotional impact of revisiting challenging situations or memories related to their involvement in campus journalism. You may decline to answer any or all questions and you may terminate your involvement at any time if you choose.

Your responses to this study will be anonymous. Please do not write any identifying information in your questionnaire. Your comments will also be anonymous. We will ensure the confidentiality of your data through obtaining informed consent, ensuring anonymity and confidentiality, securely storing data in encrypted formats, and limiting access to authorized researchers only. Respondent data will be kept confidential, except in cases where the researcher is legally obligated to report specific incidents.

If you have questions at any time about this study, you may contact the researcher(s), whose contact information, is(are) provided above.

Your participation in this study is voluntary. It is up to you to decide whether or not to take part in this study. If you decide to take part in this study, you will be asked to sign this consent form. After you sign the consent form, you are still free to withdraw at any time, and without giving any reason. If you withdraw from the study before data collection is completed, your data will be destroyed.

Republic Act 10178, also known as the Data Privacy Act of 2012, "does not apply to personal information processed for... research purposes... provided, that the personal information shall be held under strict confidentiality and shall be used only for the declared purpose."

CONSENT

I have read and understand the provided information and have had the opportunity to ask questions. I understand that my participation is voluntary and I am free to withdraw at any time, without giving a reason and without cost. I understand that I will be given a copy of this consent form. I voluntarily agree to take part in this study.

_____ Name of Participant CARLO JAY F. RUIZ	_____ _____ Signature	_____ _____ Date
_____ Name of Researcher	_____ _____ Signature	_____ _____ Date

References:
Republic Act 10173 - Data Privacy Act of 2012. <https://www.privacy.gov.ph/data-privacy-act/>
Roane State Community College. (2011). *Informed consent*. https://www.roanestate.edu/webfiles/WALLACEDA/okr/IRB/Informed_Consent%20Template.doc

APPENDIX D

Informed Consent for Minors and Parental Consent

ASSENT FOR MINORS AND PARENTAL CONSENT

Research Title: **A PHENOMENOLOGICAL STUDY OF STAKEHOLDERS' EXPERIENCES IN CAMPUS JOURNALISM IMPLEMENTATION AT SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN CAVITE**
Researcher: Carlo Jay F. Ruiz
School/Organization: University of the Philippines-Open University
Cellphone Number: 09751962996

Good day!

I am conducting research about the lived experiences of stakeholders—student journalists, advisers, and school administrators—in secondary schools in Cavite, focusing on the implementation of campus journalism programs under the Campus Journalism Act of 1991, and to examine the need for reforms in this law to adapt to the demands of modern journalism. Research is a way for us to gain new knowledge about important matters concerning people, the world, and our society. If you would like to participate in our research, we will ask you about experiences with campus journalism under the Campus Journalism Act of 1991, assess the relevance and effectiveness of the Act in the digital age while identifying necessary revisions, investigate the integration of digital media skills into journalism programs for better career preparation, and evaluate the role of campus journalism in enhancing students' critical thinking, creativity, and media literacy. for approximately one hour.

There are things you need to know. One of them is the steps we will take as part of our research, such as: 1. Permit the researcher to conduct the interview; 2. Set the time and place of the interview; and 3. Feel free to answer the questions raised during the interview.

There are benefits to participating in this study, such as the opportunity for personal reflection, empowerment through sharing their voices, contribution to policy and practice improvements, enhanced networking and skill development, increased awareness of relevant issues, recognition in research outputs, and access to valuable findings that can inform their own practices and the broader community. The risks of participating in this study are risks such as discomfort from discussing sensitive or negative experiences, concerns about confidentiality and privacy, misunderstandings regarding the study's purpose or use of their insights, possible repercussions from school administrations or peers, and the emotional impact of revisiting challenging situations or memories related to their involvement in campus journalism.

After our research, we will create a report on what we have learned. Your information will remain confidential, and no personal information will be used in our reports or shared with any organization, in accordance with the provisions of the Data Privacy Act of 2012.

If you do not wish to participate in our study, you may decline. If you change your mind while providing information, you can inform us.

If you decide to participate in this research, please write your name in the space provided:

I have read and fully understood the statements above. I voluntarily agree to participate in the research.

Name of the Participant

Signature and Date

PARENTAL CONSENT

We are asking for your permission for your child to participate in this study. Please sign below to indicate that you have understood and agree to your child's participation.

Name of the Parent/Guardian

Signature and Date

References:

Republic Act 10173 - Data Privacy Act of 2012. <https://www.privacy.gov.ph/data-privacy-act/>

Rochester Institute of Technology. (2012, September 12). *Single consent form*. https://www.rit.edu/research/irms/sample_assent_form

APPENDIX E

Interview Guide Questions

GUIDE QUESTIONS ON THE STAKEHOLDERS' EXPERIENCES AND IN CAMPUS JOURNALISM IMPLEMENTATION AT SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN CAVITE

I. Experiences in Implementation:

I. Experiences in Implementation:

1. How can you describe your experience as a student journalist under the Campus Journalism Act of 1991? Have you experience any challenges? If yes, what are they? How do you cope with these challenges?
2. What current and emerging technological advancements (e.g., social media, online publishing) relevant with campus journalism function have you observed and how do these technologies impact your work as a campus journalist?
3. Have there been any notable changes in the resources or support available for campus journalism in recent years? If so, how have those changes affected you?

II. Relevance and Effectiveness:

4. In what ways do you believe the Campus Journalism Act of 1991 remains relevant to your work today?
5. Are there any specific provisions of the Campus Journalism Act that you feel need to be updated? If there are, what are they and why do you think these changes are necessary?
6. How well do you think the current legal framework prepares you for the realities of modern journalism?

III. Integration of Digital Skills:

7. What digital media skills do you think are essential for today's student journalists, and how are these incorporated into your campus journalism program?
8. How can you describe your digital skills training experience in your current program?

IV. Role in Development:

9. How has your experience in campus journalism contributed to your critical thinking, creativity, and media literacy?
10. How does your involvement in campus journalism influenced your views on media and society today?

References:

- Republic Act 10173 - Data Privacy Act of 2012. <https://www.privacy.gov.ph/data-privacy-act/>
Roane State Community College. (2011). *Informed consent*. https://www.roanestate.edu/webfiles/WALLACEDA/olcr/IRB/Informed_Consent%20Template.doc

APPENDIX F

Interview Guide Validation

INTERVIEW GUIDE VALIDATION REPORT

	Accept	Reject	Revise	Remarks
For Student Journalists				
I. Experiences In Implementation				
1. Can you describe your experience as a student journalist under the Campus Journalism Act of 1991? What challenges have you encountered?			✓	How can you describe your experience as a student journalist under the Campus Journalism Act of 1991? Have you experience any challenges? If yes, what are they? How do you cope with these challenges?
2. How do technological advancements (e.g., social media, online publishing) impact your work as a campus journalist?			✓	What current and emerging technological advancements relevant with campus journalism function have you observed and how do these technologies impact your work as a campus journalist?
3. Have there been any notable changes in the resources or support available for campus journalism in recent years? If so, how have those changes affected you?	✓			
II. Relevance and Effectiveness				
4. In what ways do you believe the Campus Journalism Act of 1991 remains relevant to your work today?	✓			
5. Are there any specific provisions of the Campus Journalism Act that you feel need to be updated? Why?			✓	ADD: If there are, what are they and why do you think these changes are necessary?
6. How well do you think the current legal framework prepares you for the realities of modern journalism?	✓			
III. Integration of Digital skills				
7. What digital media skills do you think are essential for today's student journalists, and how are these incorporated into your campus journalism program?	✓			
8. How well are you being trained in these digital skills through your current program?			✓	How can you describe your digital skills training experience in your current program?
IV. Role in Development				
9. How has your experience in campus journalism contributed to your critical thinking, creativity, and media literacy?	✓			
10. Can you provide examples of how your involvement in campus journalism has influenced your views on media and society?			✓	How does your involvement in campus journalism influenced your views on media and society today?
For School Paper Advisers				
I. Experiences In Implementation				
1. As an adviser, what challenges have you faced in implementing campus journalism in your school?			✓	How can you describe your advising experiences in implementing campus journalism in your school? Have you experience any challenges? If yes, what are they? How do you cope with these challenges?
2. How do you perceive the impact of technological advancements on campus journalism in your school?	✓			

II. Relevance and Effectiveness				
3. How do you view the relevance of the Campus Journalism Act of 1991 in shaping the educational experiences of student journalists today?	✓			
4. What feedback do you receive from students regarding the provisions of this law? Are there common themes that emerge?			✓	What feedback do you usually receive from students regarding the provisions of this law? How do you respond to these feedbacks?
III. Integration of Digital Skills				
5. In your opinion, what digital skills should be emphasized in campus journalism programs to prepare students for future careers in the media industry?	✓			
6. How do you currently integrate these skills into your advising practices and the curriculum?	✓			ADD: Do you find them effective? If yes, what evidences of improvement have you observed?
IV. Role in Development				
7. How do you think campus journalism contributes to developing essential skills such as critical thinking and media literacy among students?			✓	*add creativity as well
8. Can you share specific instances where you've seen students grow in <u>their</u> journalistic abilities through involvement in campus journalism?			✓	What specific instances have you seen where students grow in their journalistic abilities through involvement in campus journalism?
For School Administrators				
I. Experiences in Implementation				
1. What is your perspective on the implementation of campus journalism in your school under the Campus Journalism Act of 1991?	✓			
2. How does your administration support campus journalism initiatives, and what challenges have you encountered in doing so?	✓			
II. Relevance and Effective				
3. How relevant do you find the provisions of the Campus Journalism Act in today's rapidly changing media landscape?			✓	Do you find the provisions of the Campus Journalism Act relevant in today's rapidly changing media landscape? If yes, how and at what extent?
4. Have you observed any gaps in the current law that you believe should be addressed?			✓	Add: If yes, what are they?
III. Integration of Digital Skills				
5. What role do you think digital media skills play in a comprehensive campus journalism practice?	✓			
6. In what ways do you encourage the integration of digital skills in journalism education at your school?	✓			
IV. Role in Development				
7. How do you believe campus journalism aligns with the broader educational objectives of fostering critical thinking and creativity among students?			✓	*and media literacy
8. Have you noticed an impact of campus journalism on student engagement or community involvement? If so, could you elaborate?			✓	How can you describe the impact of campus journalism on student engagement and community involvement?

CERTIFICATE OF VALIDATION

This is to certify that to the best of my knowledge and ability, I have reviewed the generated and developed interview questions for the qualitative study **“A Phenomenological Study of Stakeholders’ Experiences in Campus Journalism Implementation at Secondary Schools in Cavite”** by Mr. Carlo Jay F. Ruiz, a graduate student under Master of Development Communication program from University of the Philippines Open University.

The instrument has been checked and validated of its utility for this research and is recommended for implementation. Given this 13th of April, in the year of our Lord, two thousand twenty-five.

GIDEON LUKE P. TY, MAPs, RPsy, RPrn, LPT
Affiliate Clinical Psychologist, PsycheTrendz Psychological Services
Program Chair, NU Dasmarinas

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